

**Sustainable Solar Energy in India: A Circular Economy Approach with
Extended producer responsibility**

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Abstract

This study investigates potential strategies and systemic barriers to implementing the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) approach to create a sustainable waste management system for photovoltaic systems. Semi-structured interviews and in-person observations elucidate that significant challenges impact these programs, including unsustainable panel designs, logistical constraints, a dearth of recycling facilities, and low financial incentives to encourage recycling.

Building decentralised recycling facilities is a practical solution. These facilities can help address current logistical challenges and reduce transportation costs. Focusing on the CSTEP cluster-based strategy, the study highlights the importance of tailoring waste management programs to suit India's diverse regional contexts.

Integrating informal recyclers into the formal recycling system by offering them financial support and structured training is essential to increase safety and compliance. Mandatory buyback schemes and variable EPR charges are cost-effective strategies that ensure smooth material recovery and support environmentally friendly recycling operations.

The study also investigates emerging technologies like RFID tags, IoT-enabled tracking systems, and AI-driven sorting technology that have the potential to increase material recovery and operational efficiency significantly. Ultimately, the findings show that fostering collaboration amongst stakeholders, implementing coordinated governmental actions, and developing secondary markets for the recovered materials are essential to aligning India's solar PV waste management with the circular economy principles.

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List of Abbreviations

PV: Photovoltaic

EPR: Extended Producer Responsibility

CPCB: Central Pollution Control Board

BOS: Balance of System

CIGS: Copper-Indium Gallium-Selenide

CdTe: Cadmium Telluride

WEEE: Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment

PPP: Polluter Pays Principle

MNRE: Ministry of New and Renewable Energy

MoEFCC: Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change

IoT: Internet of Things

RFID: Radio Frequency Identification

AI: Artificial Intelligence

EPC: Engineering, Procurement, and Construction

CSR: Corporate Social Responsibility

PRO: Producer Responsibility Organization

PAYG: Pay-As-You-Go

PAYP: Pay-As-You-Put

GW: Gigawatt

TCO: Total Cost of Ownership

DG ENV: Directorate General for Environment (European Commission)

EU TCP: European Union Technical Cooperation Programme

Chapter 1- Introduction

1.1 Background

The Sun is a 4.5 billion-year-old hot glowing ball of hydrogen and helium at the centre of the solar system. Without its energy, life as we know it could not exist on our planet (NASA Science, 2017). India has a vast solar energy production capacity due to its abundant sunlight. India receives significant solar radiation, with many areas experiencing 4 to 7 kilowatt-hours of solar energy per square meter daily (Ministry of New and Renewable Energy, 2023). Thus, India is considered a prime candidate for solar power deployment.

There are on-grid and off-grid installations like rooftop solar, ground-mounted solar, floating solar, canal top solar, solar pumps, and various other innovative solar Photovoltaic-powered applications. The rapid deployment of solar PV results from a significant decline in solar electricity tariffs in the last few years compared to conventional energy sources, making it increasingly competitive (Tyagi & Kuldeep, 2021). Major initiatives like the launch of the International Solar Alliance in 2015, aimed at providing a platform for collaboration among solar resource-rich countries, led the government to witness an 11 times increase in the capacity of grid-connected solar power from 2.6 GW in 2014 to 28.18 GW in 2019 (Ministry of New and Renewable Energy, 2020).

Most of the current capacity is deployed in the southern (37 per cent) and northern parts (34 per cent). Rajasthan has 26 per cent (17 GW) installed solar capacity, followed by Gujarat, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, and Maharashtra (Tyagi & Kuldeep, 2021). India would need about 1,700 GW of solar capacity by 2050 and 5,600 GW by 2070 to achieve its 2070 net-zero target (Chaturvedi & Malyan, 2021). Even though most of the current capacity is short of decommissioning, substantial waste modules could arise from these alternative streams, such as damages during installation, operation, or natural disasters.

The Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change (MoEFCC) recently issued E-waste Management Rules 2022, mandating solar cell and module producers manage their waste (Delhi Bureau, 2024). These rules are based on extended producer responsibility. Producers must register on the official government portal and store waste generated until 2034-2035 while following Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) guidelines. Authorised recyclers are responsible for recycling (PIB, 2023b).

Responsible solar waste management requires laying the foundation for a circular economy (Tyagi et al., 2024). Solar PVs are highly recyclable, which could reduce the EOL solar PV

waste by 90% (Santos & Alonso-García, 2018). Materials recovered can be used to manufacture new PV cells and modules. Reducing the demand for virgin materials leads to decreased mining and purification of virgin materials. Additionally, PV waste management can lead to new jobs in collection, transportation, and recycling (Tyagi & Kuldeep, 2021).

1.2 Problem Statement

Given the large-scale solar energy deployment expected in the country by the end of this decade, it is imperative to focus on the waste generated from existing and future installations (Tyagi, 2020). The Indian solar industry, which began its expansion in 2010, is relatively new, with a design life of modules of 25 years. Hence, waste management is not an alarming issue. However, end-of-life is only one of the possible waste streams as PV modules observe early EOL due to various causes during their lifecycle, such as transportation and installation activities, Human errors, and poor installation and maintenance practices (Tyagi, 2020).

Solar panels can experience accelerated wear and tear, such as uneven shading across the panels, causing temperature differences that lead to faster degradation. High salt content in the ground can corrode metal frames, and loose connections, such as poorly tightened bolts and nuts, can compromise structural integrity (PV Diagnostics, 2020). Additionally, module defects during operations, like cell cracks and snail tracks in crystalline silicon modules, hot spots in thin-film modules, and back contact degradation (Köntges et al., 2014), can result in panels being discarded before their 25-year lifespan. Furthermore, natural calamities, such as typhoons, floods, and earthquakes, have destroyed several projects in India (Tyagi & Kuldeep, 2021).

Solar waste contains lead, cadmium, and tellurium materials with varying toxicity levels and monetary value. Their leaching can contaminate water and soil resources, posing risks, particularly in remote and densely populated areas (Tyagi & Kuldeep, 2021). The waste also includes high-value metals like silicon and silver, which are widely used in manufacturing (Tyagi & Kuldeep, 2021). Additionally, the health of the workforce handling collection, dismantling, and recycling is critical, as approximately 90% of e-waste collection and 70% of recycling are managed by the informal sector in India (AstuteAnalytica India Pvt. Ltd., 2024). Currently, India is not well positioned to handle PV waste, as even basic recycling facilities

for laminated glass and e-waste components are unavailable (Suresh, Singhvi and Rustagi, 2019).

The absence of established protocols for managing, recycling, and recovering materials from photovoltaic (PV) modules exacerbates India's poor recycling infrastructure. Most waste management techniques employed today are reactive, relying on the informal sector to fill gaps left by formal systems. However, the informal industry lacks the technical know-how and safety measures required to handle hazardous PV waste, including lead and cadmium, posing significant dangers to human health and the environment (Astute Analytica, 2024; Kumar and Singh, 2022).

Additionally, EPR regulations are theoretically progressive, their implementation is lacking. The absence of legally binding recycling targets and insufficient incentives for producers and recyclers are the leading causes of bottlenecks in the waste management ecosystem. Manufacturers have no incentive to produce recyclable solar panels, nor are they held accountable for gathering and recycling solar panels at the EOL. Thus, it frequently results in the loss of valuable materials like silicon and silver, which causes both ecological and economic problems (Rathore and Panwar, 2022; Fthenakis and Wang, 2020).

1.3 Aims and Objectives

This Dissertation explores how circular economy principles can be integrated into India's EPR framework to enhance sustainable solar panel waste management and address challenges such as limited recycling infrastructure, policy enforcement gaps, and the role of the informal sector.

1. To analyze the gaps in India's Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) framework in managing solar panel waste, focusing on limited recycling infrastructure and policy enforcement challenges.
2. To examine how circular economy principles can improve waste management practices within the EPR framework, drawing on best practices from global leaders in solar waste management.
3. To incorporate stakeholder insights to identify barriers and opportunities in EPR implementation.

4. To recommend strategies for integrating circular economy principles into India's solar waste management policies, addressing environmental and social challenges unique to the Indian context.

1.4 Research Questions

1. How can design innovations and material choices improve the environmental sustainability of solar panels under India's EPR framework?
2. What insights can be gained from semi-structured interviews with Solar PV stakeholders to improve collaboration and address challenges in collection and recovery?
3. What policy adjustments and infrastructure enhancements are necessary to optimize solar panel waste management while supporting circular economy principles?
4. How can business models and economic incentives make solar panel waste management profitable, scalable, and environmentally regenerative within India's EPR framework?

1.5 Dissertation structure

Chapter 1: Introduction

Outlines the study's focus on improving solar PV waste management in India through circular economy principles and EPR.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

Examines global and regional solar waste management frameworks, challenges, and circular economy applications.

Chapter 3: Methodology

Explains the use of qualitative methods, including interviews and observations, with ethical considerations and limitations.

Chapter 4: Results

Highlights findings on barriers, stakeholder insights, and logistical challenges in solar PV waste management.

Chapter 5: Discussion

Analyzes findings in relation to literature, emphasizing policy, infrastructure, and collaboration improvements.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

Summarizes key insights, provides recommendations, and suggests directions for future research.

Chapter 2: Literature review

2.1 Overview

Most of India's waste is expected to be generated from Solar PV deployed between 2024 and 2030 (Tyagi et al., 2024). However, there is still much uncertainty. While most of the current capacity is yet to reach decommissioning, substantial quantities of waste modules could arise from alternative streams, such as damages during installation, operation, or natural disasters (Suresh, Singhvi, and Rustagi, 2019).

Handling this PV waste is essential from environmental, economic, and social perspectives (Ali *et al.*, 2024). Addressing these issues requires an understanding of India's socio-economic dynamics (Roy, Jha and Bhattacharya, 2024). Additionally, new financing mechanisms and business models, stricter guidelines, stakeholder coordination, reverse logistics, storage, dismantling centres, and recycling facilities are necessary to manage this waste effectively (Arora et al., 2018). This literature review will consider previous research on Solar PV waste management and recycling to justify the rationale for the present study.

Figure 1. Environmental impact of solar value chain in India, Suresh, Singhvi and Rustagi, 2019.

This literature review is structured around six main topics of Solar PV waste, Environmental impacts, Circular economy, Global PV waste management frameworks, PV waste management in India.

2.2 Solar PV waste

Figure 2. Estimated PV waste generation by 2050, CSTEP, 2023.

A crucial study area is estimating cumulative solar PV modules (2020-2050). The literature often highlights two key divisions of solar PV waste: early loss and regular loss. Weekend, Wade and Heath (2016) projected an increase of 60 million tonnes by the end of 2050, with 60 million tonnes in a regular loss scenario and 80 million in an early loss scenario worldwide. This division is essential for understanding future waste management needs and potential pressure on recycling infrastructure.

Most PV (photovoltaic) waste consists of pre-consumer waste generated during production, manufacturing, and distribution processes, production scraps, defective panels, and damaged products before reaching consumers (International Energy Agency, 2016). According to the IEA (2016), global pre-consumer waste ranged from 43,000 to 250,000 tonnes until 2016. Waste from solar modules can be categorised according to its market value, recyclability, and environmental impact. Currently in India, the major capacity deployments are in the northern (34%) and southern (37%) regions. The next states with the largest installed solar capacity are Gujarat, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, and Maharashtra; Rajasthan accounts for 26% (17 GW) of this total (Tyagi & Kuldeep, 2021).

The input parameters used are the same across all countries as they do not capture the effect of location on module performance (Tyagi et al., 2024). Waste generated from the balance of system (BOS), including inverters, transformers, and wires, is not counted in India's MoEFCC (2022) E-waste Rules. It has a lifespan of 3 to 10 years and is expected to reach high quantities in the coming decades (Gautam & Ayush, 2021).

Thus, to bridge gaps, Tyagi et al. (2024) conducted a study in India, stating that waste estimates could lie between 100 to 700 kilotons from 2024 to 2030, depending on early and regular loss scenario modelling. The limitations of such waste modelling lie in not considering the manufacturing of PV cells and module production. Other factors are not considered, such as natural calamities and repowering through refurbishments in decommissioned panels (Tyagi et al., 2024). There are different stages where modules get damaged and are discarded, especially during transportation and installation activities. Additionally, PV panels may develop defects during operations and plant maintenance, eventually decommissioning before their 25-year lifespan (Tyagi & Kuldeep, 2021). This reflects uncertainty in PV waste tracking due to minimal waste from decommissioned solar panels, given the 25-30-year lifespan and various waste sources (Weekend, Wade and Heath, 2016).

2.3 Environmental impacts

India's most widely used solar panel technology is Crystalline silicon (C-si). Cadmium telluride (CdTe) and thin-film solar technologies are emerging technologies. Like copper-indium gallium-selenide (CIGS), solar cells have a limited share in the global market for PV installations (Suresh, Singhvi, and Rustagi, 2019).

2.3.1 The Material Composition of Solar PV

The c-Si PV module constitutes an assembly of solar cells packaged into a protective multi-layered structure. It has five major components: a front cover, an electrical circuit interconnecting solar cells, two polymer-based encapsulant layers protecting solar cells and a back cover. Additionally, aluminium metal frames are used to support the panel structure. Up to 80% of the weight of a c-Si technology solar panel comprises glass and aluminium, while the rest is lead, silver, copper and tin. PV cells also have a coating of copper in the cables. At the same time, thin film solar PV technologies have rare metals like Indium and germanium (Rathore and Panwar, 2022).

Figure 3. Material composition in a crystalline solar PV (by weight percentage), Latunussa et al., 2016

2.3.2 Environmental considerations

Solar PV might be one of the most promising renewable technologies as it is clean, flexible, silent and generates electricity for free after ROI (Divya et al., 2021). Even though the power generation stage of solar PV might involve emissions-free manufacturing and end-of-life treatment, it significantly negatively impacts the solar value chain (Suresh, Singhvi and Rustagi, 2019).

Manufacturing PV material releases byproducts such as sulfuric acid, hydrogen fluoride, and hydrochloric and nitric acid. Many other chemicals are used during cell manufacturing, and traditional silicon PV contains fewer chemicals than thin-film PV technology. Still, gallium, selenium, telluride, and Indium make disposal more environmentally hazardous than traditional PV (Rathore and Panwar, 2022).

2.3.3 Waste Management Challenges

IEA (2022) reports that most PV waste is landfilled worldwide, and only 14% of the estimated PV modules are recycled. Landfilling might be considered a legal disposal method in most regions, but it can cause loss of natural resources and soil and air pollution (Rathore and Panwar, 2022).

The "Full Recovery End-of-Life Photovoltaic" (FRELPE) process developed by an Italian company as part of the European "LIFE" program estimated 1000 kg of silicon PV waste panels, resulting in significant landfill waste (320.13 kg). Additionally, fly ash and sludge containing metallic residue required specialised disposal (Latunussa et al., 2016).

2.3.4 Environmental Impact of Specific Materials

While aluminium (Al) and silicon (Si) are comparatively less toxic, heavy metals like lead (Pb) and cadmium (Cd) are ecological and a human carcinogen (Tyagi & Kuldeep, 2021). Their leaching can lead to a loss in biodiversity, decreased growth, impacts on kidney function, and adverse reproductive and cardiovascular impacts (O., M. and N., 2007). The pH level of the surroundings plays a huge role in the leaching of metals in a landfill; however, on exposure to low PH levels (acidification), Pb and Cd leaching can increase up to 90% and 40%, respectively (European Commission, 2011).

2.3.5 Beyond metals

Glass and Polymer in solar PV raise environmental concerns. The polymer in back sheets and encapsulant layers is a sealant for solar cell modules consisting of fluorinated and cross-linked plastics (Rathore and Panwar, 2022). In their Bridge to India report, Suresh, Singhvi, and Rustagi (2019) highlight that this Polymer is challenging to recover and is incinerated. Pyrolysis, the primary industry-ready recycling process for destroying encapsulation materials, is highly energy-intensive (Rathore & Panwar, 2022). On the other hand, manufacturers use antimony to improve the stability and performance of solar panel glass. Antimony provides light-refracting characteristics, but at the end-of-life stage, panels are often exposed to wet conditions, making antimony leach from the glass, eroding the environment (Rathore and Panwar, 2022).

2.3.6 Future trends

The percentage of c-Si-type panels in the market will reduce from 80% to 44% b/w 2014 to 2030 (Sica et al., 2018). A project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program aims to reduce the consumption of raw materials used in the manufacturing of solar PV, thus reducing the carbon footprint of the modules by improving the efficiency of the entire value chain (European Commission, 2019). Advancements in research and technological developments continue to reduce the composition of hazardous and rare materials. This would improve the production process and recovery of EOL panels.

2.4 Circular economy

The increasing adoption of solar energy necessitates the development of a circular economy for solar PV modules to minimise environmental impacts and resource depletion. This approach prioritises the Design, usage, reuse, recycling, and recovery of materials throughout the PV lifecycle.

Figure 4. Lifecycle stage of Solar PV, Arora et al., 2018.

2.4.1 Recycling Techniques

Module recycling techniques compare parameters like recovery yield, energy consumption, and quantum of residual waste (Komoto and Lee, 2018). It is a multi-step process involving disassembly, the disintegration of the laminated structure (delamination), and the recovery of metals (Suresh, Singhvi and Rustagi, 2019).

Mechanical process: C-Si modules, the most widely used ones, are recycled mainly using conventional mechanical processes by glass and metal recyclers. This method can recover 70-80 percent of crystalline Silicon (c-Si) solar panel raw materials by weight (Suresh, Singhvi and Rustagi, 2019). Most recycled and recovered materials consist of lower-grade materials like glass, followed by aluminium and copper (Tyagi & Kuldeep, 2021). The recovered glass is contaminated with bits of Silicon, polymers and metals, making it unfit for manufacturing new modules. It is thus used in the glass fibre manufacturing or construction industry (Suresh, Singhvi and Rustagi, 2019).

Advanced or specialised process: PV recycling involves a mix of (mechanical, thermal, and chemical processes) to recover most materials, including glass, aluminium, copper, Silicon, silver, lead and tin. Specialised PV waste recycling is still very uncommon. Scientific studies show that up to 90-95% of PV waste is recoverable (Tyagi & Kuldeep, 2021; Suresh, Singhvi and Rustagi, 2019)

Purification of glass requires a mix of thermal and chemical processes that are usually not part of conventional glass recycling plants. Recently, NPC corporation in Japan commercialised a process that uses a hot blade to cut through the PV panel cells, separating solar panels' front glass and back sheet polymer. This process can separate the glass from the module in 40 seconds by utilising thermal energy (Lunardi et al., 2018; Spaes, 2021).

Out of all the techniques, Chemical processes provide higher recovery but are suitable for small-scale on-site operations, while mechanical and thermal processes are more suitable for bulk treatment of PV modules (Suresh, Singhvi and Rustagi, 2019; Radavičius et al., 2021). First Solar is one of the first solar companies to develop a comprehensive recycling process for their CdTe thin-film solar panels recycling program (American Progress, 2024). Korean researchers have also developed a new method to recycle silicon solar panels without using harmful chemicals like hydrofluoric acid. Recycled wafers produce solar cells with nearly the same performance as those from new Silicon (Kim et al., 2024).

Though PV recycling is still a work in progress and technologically feasible, it is still ineffective and unscalable (Rathore and Panwar, 2022). Recycled modules are adequate substitutes since they maintain about 90% of the power of new ones (Divya et al., 2021). Proactive actions from private stakeholders and policymakers are required for the sector to grow over the long run (Rathore and Panwar, 2022).

Figure 5. PV module recycling Multisteps, Tyagi and Kuldeep, 2021.

2.4.2 Life cycle assessment

Research suggests that the environmental impact of using virgin materials is more significant than using recycled materials. A life cycle assessment done of 1 tonne SI PV panels manufactured from recycled material indicated GWP production equal to 370 kg Co₂eq/kg savings around 800-1200 Co₂eq/kg in the case of modules manufactured from 100% virgin material sources (Latunussa et al., 2016). However, a study done by Maani et al. (2020) found that recycling may lead to higher impacts than using virgin materials; the reason for this uncertainty is the different recycling processes with varied impacts.

A study on solar PV waste management in India (Kumar et al., 2023) that conducted an LCA on various recycling scenarios found that advanced thermal and chemical recycling techniques significantly reduced environmental impacts, such as global warming potential, eutrophication, and acidification, when compared to conventional mechanical processes. However, the study also found tradeoffs: energy-intensive processes, such as thermal recycling, and increased energy consumption may negate any environmental benefits if non-renewable resources fueled them.

2.4.3 Design challenges

The literature highlights that panel designs are important as they play a huge role in repairing, refurbishing, dismantling or extending the life cycle. In the case of a standard PV module recycling process, recovered materials are contaminated and cannot be reused. Thus, designing panels with the end-of-life stage, i.e. easy recovery of material, labelling of product contents and recyclability and damage to the panel during dismantling collection or transport, is minimized (IEA, 2016).

Research done by Radavičius et al. (2021) proposed circularity issues, design changes, and evaluation of those design changes using a four-step approach. A workshop was conducted that highlighted the tightly sealed sandwich structure of Solar PV as the main design issue. Other issues related to strong encapsulation material between the layers, toxic material in the solar panels, and lack of relevant information accessibility during the solar panel's lifetime were also highlighted in the online workshop.

A study by Huang, Atasu and Toktay (2019) explores how EPR policies influence product design and the tradeoffs between durability and recyclability of products. While past research has primarily examined the environmental and economic impacts of EPR policies, focusing on financial mechanisms (e.g. taxes, fees), labelling and take-back schemes, this

study focuses on operational decisions in product design. It explores how take-back mechanisms drive producers to balance eco-design, especially in durability (Huang, Atasu and Toktay, 2019).

Figure 6. Structure of a silicon photovoltaic module., (Ko et al., 2023)

2.4.4 Reuse and Repair

Extending the lifeline through recycling is not enough, and combining the repairability and reusability strategy is important for the industry (Radavičius et al., 2021).

Under the Eco-Solar project, the REPTILE project aims to develop and refine the "Cell-Doctor," a system that automatically identifies and isolates non-defective areas within defective solar cells and wafers, minimizing waste and maximizing the reuse of valuable materials (European Commission, 2019). Reusability can be improved since defective panels can typically be returned to the manufacturer for examination and repair. Repairable panels can be resold as replacements or as used goods for less than the going rate (Arora et al., 2018).

Operations and maintenance (O&M) strategies are crucial for improving the lifespan and performance of Solar photovoltaics (Orosz et al., 2024). Literature highlights that O&M ensures optimal functioning, reliability, and cost efficiency. Some advanced maintenance approaches are also under development, leveraging data analytics and real-time monitoring with the help of Internet of Things technology (IoT) (Orosz et al., 2024).

2.5 Global PV waste management frameworks

The literature emphasises The Polluter Pays Principle (PPP) as a key environmental management principle for PV waste, ensuring polluters bear the cost of the environmental harm they cause. It involves shifting the financial responsibility for waste management, recycling, and disposal from governments and consumers to producers for the entire life cycle of their products. The EU WEEE Directive has inspired the PPP principle, with Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) at the heart of the directive (EU-INDIA: TCP, 2021). EPR builds on the Polluter Pays Principle (PPP) by directly holding producers accountable for managing the financial as well as operational responsibility for the entire life cycle of their products through systems such as take-back, product redesign, and waste tracking (OECD, 2001; Serpe et al., 2024).

2.5.1 Regulatory Frameworks

Through its WEEE directive, the European Union (EU) has established a global standard for PV panel EOL management. The WEEE directive was updated in 2012 to provide particular provisions for PV panels after its implementation in 2003 (Arora et al., 2018). Many countries in the EU, including Germany, Italy, and the UK, have a mature solar industry, which pushed the EU to devise this waste management regulation (Tyagi, 2020). All EU member states must abide by the revised Directive by 2014. According to European law, every EU member state must embody a directive in national law. Although every nation must adhere to the Directive's minimal standards, they are free to "gold-plate" it by including extra clauses in their national laws. For instance, Member States differ in how they carry out their financial responsibilities under the WEEE Directive (EU-INDIA: TCP, 2021).

Several European nations have implemented systems for handling photovoltaic (PV) modules' end-of-life (EOL). Depending on their capacity, PV panels are classified as either household or commercial WEEE in Italy. Historical panels (before 2014) are handled differently from new ones, subject to producer-specific recycling obligations (Malandrino *et al.*, 2017). Germany and the UK use comparable approaches, with Germany depending on manufacturers' alliances for waste collection and recycling through the Stiftung EAR system and the UK concentrating on producer registration and compliance for PV panel management (Stiftung Ear, 2022; UK Government, 2018).

Instead of having restrictions, PV waste in Japan is governed by standard waste legislation. Despite being the biggest producer of PV modules, China does not have specific waste management laws for these modules; instead, it relies on more general e-waste laws that do not address PV trash. Although no laws exist, South Korea intends to implement an Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) program by 2023, requiring manufacturers to fund recycling facilities. This is an important future development given the nation's expanding solar capacity (Arora et al., 2018; Tyagi, 2020). The Resource Conservation and Recovery Act (RCRA) in the United States treats PV modules as general hazardous waste, and no national rules mainly address PV trash (Arora et al., 2018). However, other states have considered regulations, including New York and California. PV modules have been proposed for inclusion in Universal Waste Management laws by California's Department of Toxic Substances Control (DTSC), specifically for hazardous materials such as lead and cadmium. The Solar Panel Collecting Act (2018), passed in New York, mandates that manufacturers create and fund programs for the collecting, recycling, and disposing of defective modules (US Epa, 2021).

2.5.2 Financing

Producers assume financial responsibility for photovoltaic (PV) waste management. In Business-to-consumer (B2C) transactions, producers must cover the entire waste collection, treatment, recycling, and disposal cost without involving consumers and ensuring greater efficiency, as producers directly manage the waste management process. In contrast, business-to-business (B2B) transactions allow for contractual agreements, enabling a shared cost model between producers and non-private consumers (Arora et al., 2018).

Financing models manage costs, such as pay-as-you-go (PAYG) and pay-as-you-put (PAYP). 'PAYP' requires consumers to pay an additional fee at the point of sale to cover future waste treatment costs, such as eco-fees funded by annual payments from manufacturers and distributors. At the same time, 'PAYG' involves producers taking responsibility for waste management when the waste occurs, such as taking back schemes obligating producers to collect and recycle EOL PV (EU-INDIA: TCP, 2022). Fulfilling the producer's waste collection targets is assisted by Producer responsibility organisations (PRO) established by multiple projects or independently. They use their network to manage logistics, collection, recycling and compliance (UK Government, 2018). In countries like the UK and Germany, these financing systems are executed through Producer Compliance Schemes (PCS), where producers pay fees to guarantee future recycling, helping to mitigate risks such as insolvency (EU-INDIA: TCP, 2022; Arora et al., 2018).

EPR systems are also being introduced via evolving regulatory frameworks in South Korea and Japan. An EPR program that required businesses to pay a recycling charge was rolled out in South Korea in 2023. Although conventional waste laws presently govern the handling of PV waste in Japan, new specialised restrictions are being planned. These developing solutions, which guarantee sustainable PV waste recycling, demonstrate the global movement towards producer's financial accountability (Arora et al., 2018; Tyagi & Kuldeep, 2021)

2.5.3 Efficacy

National and regional initiatives have greatly aided the advancement of the sustainability agenda. The environmental policy principle of extended producer responsibility (EPR), which calls for a network for the separate collection of e-waste, suitable management systems and infrastructures, as well as monitoring and tracking tools, was addressed by legislation in the majority of regulated countries (67 out of 81) today (Serpe *et al.*, 2024). The ProgRess program, for instance, was launched in Germany and focuses on resource efficiency and transitioning towards a circular economy, which includes recycling PV modules (lea-pPVs, 2024). These initiatives are part of a more significant movement to incorporate the recycling of PV modules into national waste management programs.

Despite these advancements, significant challenges remain in other parts of the world, particularly in countries like India and China, where formal regulations for PV waste management are still in their early stages. "Operation BlackSun," which exposed the Italy PV waste fraud, revealed weaknesses in the EU's WEEE legislation. Thousands of decommissioned photovoltaic panels that were supposed to be recycled at a factory in Sicily were illegally shipped to Senegal, Nigeria, and Syria after being falsely re-labelled as functional. The plant owner was detained for counterfeiting, money laundering, and waste trafficking after authorities confiscated 60 tons of panels (Bellini, 2020). The case highlights regulatory flaws, especially the hazy line separating "waste" from reusable items.

It is impossible to undervalue the significance of product labelling and reporting in these standards. For companies to steer customers toward appropriate disposal procedures and prevent PV modules from being disposed of with unorganised household waste, labels containing symbols such as the crossed-out wheeled bin and producer identification are essential (Arora et al., 2018). To ensure that environmental regulations are followed and recovery rates are tracked, the WEEE Directive also mandates that producers maintain

records of sales, returns, and waste treatment (EU-INDIA: TCP,2021). This is particularly relevant in nations like Italy, where strict reporting procedures and legislation mandate that producers handle the waste of PV panels installed after 2014 (Arora et al., 2018). The directive, however, provides relaxation in collection targets to a few member countries like Bulgaria, Latvia, Hungary, and Poland because of the lack of necessary infrastructure and EEE consumption (Tyagi, 2020).

By encouraging producers to design PV modules with recyclability in mind, the EU's Eco-Design Directive reinforces these efforts and enhances the efficacy of future processes for recycling (Rossi & Solarpower Europe, 2024). This directive seeks to encourage sustainable design practices across industries and minimise waste at initial stages by establishing precise standards for product design that consider the concept of urban mining of materials. Similarly, PV waste can only be dumped in landfills if adequately treated and recycled, according to the Landfill Directive. This rule focuses on removing dangerous materials like lead and recovering valuable materials like silver and indium to reduce the environmental impact of landfilling (EU-INDIA: TCP, 2021).

2.5.4 Industry Initiative

PV Cycle, a not-for-profit industry organisation, pioneered PV module recycling before formally revising the WEEE directive to include PV modules in the EEE waste category. This was a producer-driven initiative within the EU, with PV Cycle offering recycling, take-back, and waste disposal, tailored to comply with different WEEE regulations across various countries (EU-INDIA: TCP, 2021). Despite the efforts to harmonise the approach across the EU, the implementation differs, causing an imbalance for multinational producers in abiding by specific regulations per country (Serpe et al., 2024). To oversee business-to-business (B2B) recycling initiatives for PV modules, PV Cycle works as an authorised Producer Compliance Scheme (PCS) in the UK and partners globally, most notably with JPV Collection in Japan (Tyagi, 2020). Similarly, First Solar, a well-known PV manufacturer, has established a global recycling program that recovers up to 90% of materials, including semiconductors and glass. In addition to its own in-house recycling systems, First Solar collaborates with academic institutions and industry players to develop PV recycling technologies (First Solar, 2022).

Country/Region	Regulatory Framework	Key Challenges	Industry Initiatives
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European Union	WEEE Directive mandates PV recycling.	Variations in implementation across member states.	PV Cycle: Recycling and take-back schemes.
Germany	WEEE Directive implemented; ambitious PV targets set for 2030 and 2040.	High transport costs for take-back logistics; need for expanded recycling infrastructure.	Improved coordination of collection systems; expanded recycling for non-silicon modules.
United Kingdom	PV waste under WEEE Directive.	High compliance costs for small producers.	PV Cycle PCS network supports recycling.
Japan	Governed by general waste laws.	High recycling costs; no PV-specific laws.	JPV Collection partnerships for recycling.
India	E-Waste Rules, 2022, with EPR provisions.	Informal sector dominance; lack of infrastructure.	Tata and Vikram Solar's limited initiatives.
United States	State-specific efforts like California's Act.	Lack of uniform federal policy.	First Solar: In-house recycling program.

Table 1. Global Comparison PV waste management

2.6 PV waste management in India

Solar is getting cheaper in India. India's Solar capacity has grown 26 times in the last 10 years, reaching 73.32 GW in December 2023 (PIB, 2023). This trend will continue as 292 GW of installed solar capacity is expected by 2030. Given this sizable solar deployment in India by the end of this decade, the issue of solar waste is imperative. The cumulative waste from existing and new capacity (2024-2030) will reach about 600 kilotons by 2030 (Tyagi et al., 2024). Solar PV waste in India has been identified as a neglected sector, followed by an unregularised, unscientific, and informal approach (Jain, Sharma, and Gupta, 2022).

Recognising the criticality of this issue, Jain, Sharma, and Gupta (2022) examined the end-of-life (EOL) management of solar PV waste in India, emphasising the need for regulatory framework development. It highlighted the need for a multi-stakeholder approach involving government agencies, manufacturers, recycling companies, and consumers (Jain, Sharma and Gupta, 2022). The framework proposed for India is based on the EPR principle, with the government overseeing the integration of stakeholders. Manufacturers are given the financial responsibility of handling the waste.

The current E-waste Rules 2022 regulations must comprehensively address the full spectrum of PV waste, especially the Balance of Systems (BoS) components, excluded from existing policies (Jain, Sharma & Gupta, 2022). Other concerns, like the absence of clear penalties for noncompliance, potentially reduce the policy's impact (Arora et al., 2018).

There is also a resource challenge in the sector as critical metals like silicon, germanium, and lithium, which are used in manufacturing solar panels, lead to competition and supply

crunch (Arora et al., 2018). However, the high recyclability rates of the constituent materials of solar PVs could reduce the EOL solar PV waste by 90% (Santos and Alonso-García, 2018).

The socio-economic impacts of PV module recycling are massive, particularly in developing countries like India, where the informal e-waste sector dominates. Transitioning to a more formalised and regulated PV waste management system could improve the industry and create more jobs (Tyagi & Kuldeep, 2021). It could also reduce environmental risks by ensuring that hazardous materials are handled safely, addressing economic and environmental sustainability (European Commission DG ENV, 2011).

2.6.1 EPR in India

The e-waste management policy for solar PV modules is an uncompromised step towards a more sustainable solar energy landscape; there are areas for improvement: stronger enforcement measures, better integration of the informal sector through centralisation of the e-waste sector, improving collection infrastructure for cost-effective transportation, lack of defined recycling targets or standardised recycling benchmarks, low technology with lack of profitable business opportunities (CSTEP, 2023).

India's E-Waste (Management) Rules of 2022 included regulations for managing solar photovoltaic (PV) waste, mandating solar PV modules and cell producers to store waste generated from their products through EPR until 2034–2035 (MoEFC, 2022). Despite the proactive steps, these regulations have several flaws, as the extended timeline for compliance until 2034–2035 may delay the implementation of effective recycling systems (PIB, 2023a). Additionally, the rapid growth of solar installations could lead to a massive increase in PV waste generation, potentially outpacing the development of the required infrastructure (Kumar & Sharma, 2021).

The Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), which aims to reduce the overall amount of waste reaching landfills by placing the responsibility of managing the EOL solar PV waste on manufacturers, is the most effective widely adopted approach (EU-INDIA: TCP, no date). However, an informal and illegal sector for managing the e-waste take-back system hampers circularity and requires regulation (Dwivedy, Suchde and Mittal, 2015). Additionally, compliance with EPR policies for solar waste management poses additional expenses for producers, eventually passed on to end-users (Monier, 2014), creating hurdles for developing countries like India with price-sensitive markets.

The literature highlights the importance of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) and the crucial role of Producer Responsibility Organizations (PROs) in streamlining the collection, transportation, and recycling of end-of-life solar panels. There is significant scope for drawing from global best practices, such as the WEEE directive, which discusses design improvements in eco-labelling and can provide valuable insights for India to build a more robust infrastructure for recycling and waste management (OECD, 2022).

Key challenges in implementing Indian EPR for PV waste management include coordination among various stakeholders, lack of transparency, low regulatory pressure, and the dominance of informal waste management sectors (Sharma, 2022). Furthermore, the low volumes of solar PV waste deter recyclers from investing in infrastructure and developing viable business models for recycling (IEA-PVPS, 2022). Leading manufacturers like REC and Vikram Solar, who are also members of PV Cycle, have institutional initiatives aimed at recycling their products. Tata Power Solar demonstrates its commitment to sustainability in India's renewable energy sector by implementing an EPR framework that raises e-waste management awareness and ensures regulatory compliance. Their efforts, highlighted in sustainability reports, integrate the circular economy and set a benchmark for ethical solar PV waste management (Tatapower, 2024). However, the overall recycling rates remain severely low (Tyagi & Kuldeep, 2021).

2.7 Related Works

The study conducted by (Jain, Sharma, and Gupta, 2022) on the end-of-life management of solar PV waste in India describes the need for a strategy to manage waste. Also, it reviews the solar PV waste management sector. The opportunities for circularity in the sector and current business viability were discussed. After expert panel evaluation, it proposes a DPSIR framework, which considers multiple stakeholders and a multisectoral approach to tackle solar PV waste. The role of institutions like MNRE and WEEE was well highlighted, and the importance of accounting for all components of PV systems, like Balance of Systems, which is not included in the Indian context, was emphasised. Additionally, the work being done by European directives and companies was discussed, along with criticism of the illegal e-waste management structure in India and the difficulty in coordination among stakeholders. This study gives a picture of the solar waste management sector but faces challenges that may hinder its applicability.

A survey done by Nain and Kumar in 2020, in a study about consumer awareness and outlook of PV, revealed critical insights into the understanding and participation of both consumers and manufacturers in solar PV waste management in India. It found that consumer awareness could be higher, with 40% of respondents unaware of the types of PV technologies available and 27% unfamiliar with the hazardous materials like lead and cadmium in solar panels. Despite this, consumers were very willing to participate in recycling initiatives, with 60% believing that the government should manage solar waste and 23% expressing readiness to contribute to recycling efforts if incentivised (Nain and Kumar, 2020).

In contrast, manufacturers were highly aware of solar panel materials, with 90% knowledgeable about their composition, including hazardous metals. However, their engagement in recycling efforts could have been higher, as many chose to dispose of end-of-life (EoL) panels through informal recyclers or second-hand sellers. Only 23% of manufacturers were willing to take responsibility for recycling, indicating a gap between awareness and active participation in formal recycling systems. This highlighted a critical reliance on informal waste management methods, complicating the sector's effective recycling and sustainability efforts. This indicates that it may be possible to pay some prepaid recycling costs during purchase under producer compliance schemes like EPR. However, understanding the government-consumer-manufacturer relationship is required to identify the issues (Nain and Kumar, 2020).

Another study by Kabir *et al.* (2023) focused on understanding blockers for EPR in developing countries. Bangladesh was used as a sample, and 65 people, including government officials, private companies, recyclers, and local authorities, were surveyed. The results showed many benefits of promoting eco-friendly designs, creating recycling infrastructure and public support. However, weak waste collection, the informal sector and low enforcement of policies hindered the process. Suggestions were made to establish targeted regulations and capacity building for effective EPR adoption (Kabir *et al.*, 2023).

A study by Radavičius *et al.* (2021) discusses the technological design challenges of PV modules. Under this research, the CIRCUSOUL project conducted a workshop, and N.I.C.E (reopenable panels) and RFID technology (information storage and access to materials) proved to be the most impactful design changes for higher circularity of the PV module (Radavičius *et al.*, 2021; Einhaus *et al.*, 2018).

The CSTEP (2023) study focuses on solar PV waste management in India by comparing three approaches to clustering PV plants for recycling purposes. The two manual methods

adopted in the study, namely, clustering based on installed capacity or district-wise cumulative capacity, have certain limitations, such as ignoring transport costs, geographical spread, and future capacity growth. Furthermore, this research highlights the need for a monitoring and reporting (M&R) system to track waste generation and recycling progress, facilitating close coordination among various stakeholders. The study highlights that economic viability can be achieved by incentivising recycling through investing in R&D and supporting the latest technologies, such as IoT, AI and robotics, for efficient segregation and waste monitoring. Collaboration with supply chain stakeholders is key to developing a robust and sustainable solar PV waste management system (Center for Study of Science, Technology and Policy, 2023).

The European Union Technical Cooperation Programme (2021) report highlights global best practices for managing solar PV waste and the challenges of implementing EPR regulations in developing countries. It highlights the need for financial incentives, phased recycling targets, and lessons acquired from the WEEE Directive for Indian regulations. A TCP, SolarPower Europe, NSEFI, and PV Cycle survey highlighted economic barriers. These included various funding options, costly transportation, and a dearth of recycling incentives. Only 7% of firms were ready to implement, even though 80% supported EPR. In order to promote sustainability and economic feasibility, stakeholders cited landfill fees, better reverse logistics, decentralised infrastructure, and stricter regulations.

The International Energy Agency's Photovoltaic Power Systems Program (IEA PVPS) research evaluates the recycling status of PV modules in global markets, emphasizing advanced material recovery techniques and state-of-the-art recycling technologies in industrialized countries. It also identifies challenges such as low waste volumes that hinder investments in recycling infrastructure (IEA PVPS, 2022).

The WEEE Forum study examines the challenges of solar panel compliance with the WEEE Directive, emphasizing the need for specific collection objectives and improved PV panel flow monitoring. It identifies gaps in financial and logistical systems while advocating for open regulatory frameworks to ensure proper collection and recycling. These lessons may prove invaluable for addressing India's informal recycling methods and integrating official procedures (WEEE Forum, 2021).

The decentralised recycling strategy in South Korea illustrates how to increase recycling rates by utilising regional collection centres. This technique improves accessibility and drastically lowers logistical expenses, especially in rural areas. By integrating informal and

formal recyclers, the system offers a scalable solution for nations with different geographic challenges, such as India. South Korea's strategy emphasises regional solutions and offers practical insights for resolving India's logistical obstacles and infrastructure deficiencies (Kim and Park, 2018).

2.7.1 Research Gap

While extensive solar PV waste management research has been conducted in Europe, particularly in countries like Germany, India's context remains underexplored. Existing research neglects the perspectives of critical stakeholders, such as installers, recyclers, and other key players in the Solar PV supply chain. This limited scope fails to manage the complexities of India's solar waste ecosystem, especially the lack of regulated recycling infrastructure and the informal sector's significant but often overlooked role.

Furthermore, waste management frameworks in Indian research hardly ever include circular economy principles. Despite providing a foundation, regulations like the E-Waste (Management) Rules, 2022 do not provide clear penalties for noncompliance, defined recycling standards, or strategies for integrating circular practices into Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) systems.

This research seeks to address these gaps, uncover actionable insights, and offer practical strategies for boosting solar panel waste management in India by incorporating semi-structured interviews with additional methods like previous observations and report evaluations. It aims to develop practical, sustainable solutions tailored to India's solar PV waste challenges by aligning stakeholder perspectives with circular economy principles.

Chapter 3- Methodology

3.1 Introduction

The literature review identified significant gaps in understanding India's solar PV waste management and circularity. While regulatory frameworks like Extended Producer

Responsibility (EPR) show potential, the country faces challenges such as insufficient limited recycling infrastructure, waste projections, and a lack of stakeholder collaboration. This study explores how circular economy principles, such as eliminating waste, reusing materials, and regenerating natural systems, can be effectively applied to India's EPR framework for solar panel recycling. Addressing these gaps requires insights from diverse stakeholders, including recyclers, Engineering, Procurement, and Construction installers, and informal recyclers, whose roles often go unexamined.

The study uses a mixed-methods qualitative approach. The primary technique for gathering data is semi-structured interviews, strengthened by general real-world observations of waste management operation challenges, such as those faced by India's informal recyclers, and technological advancements witnessed at the London Recycling Expo. Also existing literature was reviewed to fill the gaps and provide validation to the insights. These techniques offer a comprehensive overview of solar PV waste management in India, enabling the input of ideas from various stakeholder viewpoints, legislative frameworks, and practical applications.

The study has four research questions:

1. How can design innovations and material choices improve the environmental sustainability of solar panels under India's EPR framework?
2. What insights can be gained from semi-structured interviews with Solar PV stakeholders to improve collaboration and address challenges in collection and recovery?
3. What policy adjustments and infrastructure enhancements are necessary to optimise solar panel waste management while supporting circular economy principles?

4. How can business models and economic incentives make solar panel waste management profitable, scalable, and environmentally regenerative within India's EPR framework?

This methodology chapter outlines the research method used to collect the data. It contains information about the participants and how the data was gathered and analysed. The rationale for the research methods and the chosen data analysis method will also be covered.

The methods used in this study will be justified, drawing on the broader methodological theory. The chapter will also discuss the ethical considerations followed during the research.

3.2 Research Approach

The focus is on four key areas

- Circular Design and Usage for EPR
- Circular Recovery for EPR
- Multilevel stakeholder Collaborations
- Economic Considerations for EPR

3.2.1 Primary Method: Semi-Structured Interviews

Semi-structured interviews (see Appendix 4) were conducted with stakeholders, including manufacturers, recyclers, policymakers, and industry experts. The interviews explored barriers to circular recovery, policy enforcement gaps, and stakeholder collaboration. This method provided in-depth, qualitative insights that are particularly valuable for capturing stakeholders' diverse challenges in India's solar waste management ecosystem. Close coordination with all actors in the supply chain of Solar PV is an inherent component of EPR (EU-INDIA: TCP, 2021). Thus, conducting interviews to get insights into the industry and understanding the potential and barriers was crucial to bridge the gaps in the supply chain.

3.2.2 Supplementary method

A review of existing literature and reports highlighted in the related works to fulfil the gaps and provide broader perspectives for the discussion section was carried out. Additionally,

general real world observations were made to help examine the efficacy of managing e-waste. Observations in Delhi's informal sector, which exposed unregulated recycling practices, logistical strengths, and safety measure gaps, directly addressed Research Question 2 on stakeholder collaboration. The London Recycling Expo (see Appendix 1) showcased cutting-edge AI and IoT-enabled systems that shed light on Research Question 3 and 4 on infrastructure upgrades.

Surveying is considered the alternative approach; it is not used in this research since it applies to well-researched topics with well-defined variables. The open-ended nature of the research requires flexibility from interviews to unravel information on the stakeholders' experiences and systemic challenges. This research ensures interviewee privacy, so rather than using focus groups, it allows participants to speak candidly without worrying about other group dynamics.

Ultimately, the mixed-method approach successfully revealed meaningful information, fitting the study's objectives, and addressed the need for a multidimensional understanding of the challenges and opportunities in solar PV waste management in India.

3.2.3 Limitations

Collecting data from a small sample of participants, as in this study, can sometimes raise questions about reliability, validity, and generality (Chowdhury, 2014). Qualitative methods also have inherent limitations, like the subjective nature of qualitative data and the influence of the researcher's interpretations in achieving objectivity (Choy, 2014). While the study faced geographic challenges and language barriers in engaging with informal recyclers and thus could not include their inputs, general real world observations in Delhi's informal sector provided critical insights into their practices. The involvement of more extensive strategies could provide broader insights, especially in complex issues like solar PV waste management. To tackle the issue, future research could consider complementing interviews with targeted surveys and analysing emerging technologies and policy impacts to expand insights into solar PV waste management.

3.4 Data Collection and Management

Data collection for the research involved conducting in-depth interviews using a purposive sampling approach to ensure diverse stakeholders associated with solar PV waste management. The participants were selected through purposive sampling from a heterogeneous group of people, including EPC contractors, industry leaders, and stakeholders from both organisations and external agencies, from which insights could be gathered (see appendix 2).

The study prioritised geographical diversity, engaging stakeholders from various regions of India. Potential participants were identified using LinkedIn searches, professional references, and personal networks, ensuring substantial expertise and experience in the solar industry. This method enabled this research to capture rich, context-specific responses, offering deep insights into the issues. These interviews provided detailed qualitative data. Given geographic constraints, interviews were conducted virtually via Microsoft Teams, and each interview lasted 45 minutes to an hour. Interviews were recorded with Ethical consent (see Appendix 3) for transcription and coding.

The information obtained from interviews was supported by important perspectives provided by general real world observations. Observations of Delhi's informal sector operations revealed inefficiencies in solar panel recycling, unregulated dismantling practices, and the logistical dominance of informal recyclers. The London Recycling Expo introduced attendees to cutting-edge recycling technologies and emphasised how automation and artificial intelligence are advancing the circular economy concepts.

3.4.1 Anonymisation of Data

Personal information for the study, including opinions, job experiences, and, in some cases, names and contact details for interview scheduling, was gathered through in-depth interviews. Identifiers such as names or email addresses were removed from the responses to preserve privacy. Confidentiality was maintained during transcribing by keeping Stakeholder identifiers, such as names and contact details, separate from interview content. Responses were anonymised using unique codes, such as S1 and S2. Any potentially identifying information was redacted. Direct quotes used in the dissertation were reviewed

and anonymised to protect participant identity. To prevent accidental linkage, interview recordings, transcripts, and contact details were stored in separate, secure folders.

3.4.2 Participant Rights and Withdrawal

Participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any moment before the analytical phase. If participants wish to withdraw, their information will be immediately deleted from all records. This provision was made explicit in the participant information sheet and permission form (see appendix 2 and 3).

3.4.3 Data Security

All digital data, including consent forms, recordings, and transcripts, was securely stored on an encrypted server in a two-factor authentication password-protected account. To ensure strict confidentiality, the data was only accessible to the researcher.

3.4.4 Post-Research Data Management

According to university policies, data will be securely stored for six months after the dissertation submission. After this retention period, all digital files will be deleted entirely from storage systems to ensure destruction and maintain secrecy.

3.5 Data Analysis

The data collected from six semi-structured interviews was analysed using thematic analyses. As a qualitative method, thematic analysis groups common themes in the data and identifies key patterns (Boyatzis, 1998). The semi-structured Interviews were transcribed, and the transcripts were coded manually using Word. The codes were then grouped into recurring themes and sub-themes accordingly. The most appropriate themes for the research questions were then selected for the results chapter (see Appendix 5).

The limited sample size and the time needed to learn and apply such tools adequately prevented the use of qualitative analysis software, such as NVivo. Manual transcription and coding, which fits the study's time and scope limits, makes closer engagement with the data possible. Although software-based approaches might provide more features, the manual method guarantees an easier and more efficient analysis.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

The University of Surrey's ethics committee granted ethical consent for this research. Informed approval was obtained from all participants before the semi-structured interviews, with each participant receiving an information sheet outlining the study's purpose and the use of their data (See appendix 3). General real-world observations, which did not involve personal data, were excluded from ethical review but adhered to ethical guidelines. The study followed the guidelines set by the SSP as a part of the ethical approval process. To protect confidentiality, all private identifiers were removed from the data, ensuring that no responses were subjected to individual participants. Interviews were anonymised, and recordings and transcripts were securely stored and deleted after the completion of the project.

3.7 Summary of Methodology

This study employed semi-structured interviews to gather qualitative data from six stakeholders in India's solar PV waste management sector. Using purposive sampling, participants are selected for their expertise and geographic diversity, including EPC contractors, industry leaders, and stakeholders from the researcher's previous organisation and external agencies. The interviews focused on solar PV waste management challenges, stakeholder collaboration, and policy frameworks related to Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR). Supplementary information was obtained from general actual world observations.

Data collected was transcribed, coded manually, and analysed using thematic analysis to identify key patterns and themes relevant to the research questions. Ethical approval was

obtained from the University of Surrey's ethics committee, and informed consent will be obtained from all participants. Anonymising data ensured confidentiality, and recordings and transcripts were securely stored.

Chapter 4- Results

The results of this study are organized into five key themes identified through thematic coding of stakeholder interviews. These results are supported by general real world observations and previous literature on PV waste management. Additional unique themes were also identified, representing insights that extend beyond the primary categories. While the themes are presented individually for clarity, they often interconnect and collectively inform the answers to the research questions in the discussion.

4.1 Key Themes

4.1.1 Collection and Disposal Challenges for Solar Panels

All the stakeholders agreed that there are collection and disposal challenges for Solar panels after they become waste. When asked about particular challenges, **S2** said, *'There was Non-segregation at source, No separate disposal option and Awareness amongst municipal workers and ragpickers, No collection provision from rural areas, Less value of e-waste, No exchange policy and Difficult mechanism for disposal especially in the mountains'*. The CSTEP (2023) study supports these findings by pointing out the absence of remote collection sites and the logistical inefficiencies that make handling solar waste difficult.

When asked about Disposal practices at the Solar installation site, all the stakeholders raised concerns. **S5** stated that *'Broken panels during transport or installation often end up as unutilised waste'*. **S6** said, *'Handling sharp-edged panels without proper training poses safety hazards. Panels are treated as bare industrial scrap; there's no safety aspect being taken care of'*. The EU TCP (2021) report, which promotes landfill bans and mandatory safety measures to lessen these hazards, highlights similar problems in emerging solar industries.

S3 highlights the informal sector's role as a key barrier to the collection disposal of solar panels *'The informal collection network is intricate and highly optimised for cost. S3 also stated that We channel around 40-50% of our waste from these informal recyclers, and Collection centres could help integrate formal and informal recycling sectors'*. According to the CSTEP (2023) study, informal networks dominate India's solar waste management. It also emphasises the need for their integration into formal systems to increase efficiency and safety. Similarly, in order to reduce the health and environmental risks associated with unregulated recycling, the EU TCP (2021) encourages the formalisation of informal activities.

Observations of Delhi's informal e-waste sector further illustrated these challenges. Informal recyclers, or "kabadiwalas," operate efficient door-to-door collection networks but rely on hand disassembly methods without the necessary safety gear. Workers were exposed to hazardous materials like lead and cadmium, and glass fragments and non-recyclable parts were disposed of improperly in landfills or by burning. In India's e-waste ecosystem, informal recyclers remain indispensable despite these limitations, serving as the primary collectors, even for authorized recyclers. Sica et al. (2018) found similar issues in other developing countries where inadequate safety measures seriously endanger informal workers' health.

4.1.2 Stakeholder collaborations for Solar PV waste management

Stakeholder collaboration is a key theme for solar PV waste management, with input from various stakeholders. **S2** talked about the need for *'better enforcement of policies, better monitoring, subsidy, and recycling infrastructure'* from the government. **S3** also mentioned how *"when the policies are made, you take stakeholders," stressing the importance of including recyclers and informal workers. S4* added that a *"centralized regulatory framework" is needed to streamline efforts across states*, while **S5** highlighted the need for coordination between state and central governments to improve recycling policies.

Businesses were seen as important contributors to waste management. According to **S2**, they should *"use eco-friendly solar panels, implement buy-back schemes, and allocate CSR funds for recycling."*

Local communities have a role in making solar waste management more effective. **S2** suggested they *"adopt affordable solar energy and assist in recycling of solar waste."* To spread awareness, they recommended using *"community radio, posters, television, newspapers, and schools."* Incentives like *"better exchange offers"* and encouraging local ragpickers to buy solar waste were also proposed. **S4** mentioned that *'awareness*

campaigns in local languages could help increase engagement.' **S3** highlighted the importance of integrating informal collectors, stating, *'The government needs to onboard informal collectors and formalize them through monetary incentives.'* Similarly, **S5** emphasized that *'Integrated recycling strategies involving all stakeholders can make the system more efficient.'*

The London Recycling Expo further underscored the importance of multi-stakeholder collaborations. To close structural gaps, keynote discussions on circular economy strategies focused on collaborations between governments, businesses, and communities.

Collaboration between stakeholders came up often. **S4**, **S5**, and **S6** agreed that *"manufacturers, EPC companies, and recyclers need to come together for comprehensive waste management solutions."* **S5** noted this would help *"reduce logistics costs and improve collection efficiency."* **S4** discussed examples like Jamshedpur's e-waste management models involving public private partnership for solar waste management could address gaps. Pilot projects involving different stakeholders were also mentioned as ways to tackle challenges. Another illustration to address collaboration is the recommendation to build data-sharing platforms to track waste flows and maximize resource distribution (CSTEP, 2023).

Education and capacity building were highlighted too. **S2** said NGOs can play a big role in *"awareness, sensitization, and capacity development."* **S4** suggested that educational institutions could use discarded solar panels for training and experimentation.

Some gaps in the system were also mentioned. **S6** felt that *"the complete value chain is not being involved in this particular thing,"* while **S1** talked about how *"collaboration helps manage transportation and distance challenges through a network of suppliers."*

European countries are well known for their collaborative approaches to bringing together manufacturers, recyclers, and municipalities as outlined in (IEA-PVPS, 2024:IRENA (2016).

4.1.3 Policy implementation challenges in Solar PV waste management

Policy challenges emerged as a significant barrier to effective solar PV waste management, particularly in terms of compliance, awareness, and implementation. Many stakeholders expressed limited awareness of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) policies. While they acknowledged the existence of EPR, most had not observed its practical implementation. Only **S3** demonstrated a thorough understanding of the policy, stating, *"It's a great policy on paper, but it has to take into account the social, political, and economic*

realities of the area.” **S3** also highlighted the long-term nature of such regulations, noting, “Policymakers have to acknowledge the fact that it might take 10 to 20 years before the regulation can be implemented, as it was envisioned.”

The lack of clarity and practical execution was a recurring concern. **S1** said that “the EPR rules are more focused on manufacturers, not installers.” They also emphasized gaps in understanding, saying, “There’s a lack of clarity, lack of knowledge, and lack of resources in the implementation of EPR policies.” The absence of mandatory recycling goals and state-by-state explicit compliance frameworks exacerbates these issues and creates significant operational gaps (MoEFC, 2022).

S2 proposed a couple of solutions to address these challenges, suggesting that part of the subsidy provided through solar programs by the Ministry could be allocated to compensate for the cost of compliance with EPR. **S2** also recommended making compliance with EPR mandatory as for receiving licenses or certifications and integrating it into the terms and conditions for government tenders.

The absence of specific frameworks for managing solar waste and decommissioning projects was another major issue. Both **S4** and **S5** highlighted this gap, with **S4** stating, “There’s no particular policy or framework which sees in a particular manner how developers should decommission projects.” **S5** added by saying there is a need for “a centralized regulatory framework to streamline solar waste management across states.” Similarly, Michael and Iyer (2022) noted that the lack of policy-driven incentives is one of the primary barriers to developing improved recycling technologies and collection. Although the E-Waste (Management) Rules, 2022, are progressive, they lack thorough implementation advice and do not address the Balance of System (BoS) components like transformers and inverters.

Stakeholders also noted the informal sector’s dominance as a barrier to formalizing recycling systems. Stakeholders talked about Implementation gaps in broader waste management policies. **S6** observed that “there are e-waste management rules, but they are not being implemented in a proper manner.” Stricter regulations and detailed implementation guidelines were called for, with **S6** suggesting that the Ministry of New and Renewable Energy “should enforce detailed guidelines to manage decommissioning” and adopt comprehensive policies with financial incentives like tax benefits to ensure proper waste management.

While stakeholders recognized the potential of existing policies like EPR, the consensus was that their implementation required more clarity, resources, and stakeholder engagement. **S3**

summarized the issue, stating, “*Presently, EPR is not being implemented the way it was envisioned.*”

4.1.4 Economic and Technological Considerations for Solar PV waste management

Stakeholders agreed that transport costs for damaged panels often exceed their value, creating a financial burden. **S1** explained, ‘*The transport cost and risks associated with broken panels make proper disposal commercially draining, and there is no streamlined way to dispose of the waste.*’ Hence, we just leave those at the site or to the local scrap dealer.’

S5 highlighted the cost-intensive nature of recycling, stating, ‘*The recycling process can sometimes cost more than the module's current market value.*’ To address these challenges, they emphasized the need for localized recycling facilities, which could ‘reduce logistical hurdles and costs.’

S2 suggested that ‘*using metals in the body that have a higher market value*’ could make recycling processes more practical and profitable. **S5** underscored the need for labeling panels to simplify recycling, explaining that ‘*Labelling panels with contact details for buyback can simplify recycling processes.*’

S3 and **S4** stressed the importance of establishing proper infrastructure for effective solar PV waste management. **S3** highlighted the need for ‘*special recycling infrastructure for solar recycling*’ and the role of ‘*collection centers*’ in integrating formal and informal recycling sectors. They also suggested implementing ‘*mandatory recycling or buyback of old solar by manufacturing companies*’ to ensure accountability. The CSTEP model recommends positioning collection sites near areas with high solar energy potential to reduce these expenses and improve access to formal recycling systems.

S4 and **S5** reinforced this point, stating that ‘*collection centers and small recycling units are essential for cost-effective operations*’ and could ‘*reduce logistical costs and enhance efficiency.*’ Vestia Sorting Yard's automated and remotely operated recycling hubs at the Expo provided local governments with adaptable infrastructure, reduced logistical expenses, and centralized monitoring for waste sorting at the municipal and metropolitan levels. These hubs could be a source of inspiration for decentralized solutions for India's semi-urban areas, even though they were designed for organized institutions. Goupil and First mile's zero-emission vehicles also demonstrated sustainable collection options for small-scale waste in urban areas.

S6 highlighted challenges in material segregation, explaining that *'Recycling and handling of waste is a very critical issue in this particular segment.'* They added, *'It has to be segmented... glass goes to a separate vendor, aluminium frame to a separate vendor.'*

Stakeholders emphasized the need for stricter regulations and detailed implementation guidelines. **S6** suggested that *'the Ministry of New and Renewable Energy should enforce detailed guidelines to manage decommissioning'* and introduce comprehensive policies with **tax benefits** to incentivize proper waste management. These statements support the findings of Jain, Sharma, and Gupta (2022), who emphasized the critical need for government incentives such as tax rebates and subsidies to reduce financial strains and encourage compliance.

London Recycling Expo Extensively highlighted cost-effective ways to expand recycling efforts. Among the strategies employed to finance upgraded systems were utilizing green subsidies, implementing tax exemptions for compliance, and promoting public-private partnerships. **S2** recommended leveraging Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) funding, suggesting that *'CSRs can work on it and fund projects related to solar panel recycling; it should be mandatory for CSRs to deal in solar.'*

Technology was identified as a critical tool for improving solar PV waste management. **S4** highlighted that *'AI and robotics can segregate waste directly at sites, saving transportation and labor expenses.'* They further explained that *'AI-driven robotic systems for on-site waste segregation can significantly reduce costs.'*

S4 also emphasized the importance of tracking systems, stating that *'Increased tracking via RFID or IoT systems can ensure proper handling and recycling.'* Additionally, they noted that IoT-based lifecycle management is essential for streamlining recycling processes and enhancing efficiency. Technologies driven by IoT and AI can help make recycling easier by streamlining material sorting, which reduces labour costs and boosts recovery rates (Kayalvizhi et al., 2024).

The expo's Technology Zone demonstrated how technologies like blockchain for tracking waste streams may increase transparency and compliance, while public-private partnerships were highlighted as essential for funding and expanding innovative solutions.

Recycleye's artificial intelligence (AI)-powered sorting devices were particularly noteworthy at the expo as instruments that could handle complicated e-waste materials and increase material recovery rates for WEEE. IoT-enabled devices, like the smart bins in Tower Hamlets, showed how waste collection routes may be optimized with real-time monitoring.

Stakeholders recognized how these technologies could improve adherence to Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) frameworks. Cost and scalability, however, continue to be obstacles to mass adoption in India.

4.1.5 Future Outlook on Solar PV waste management

Stakeholders provided insights into the future of solar waste management especially for infrastructure needs, policy gaps, and the role of collaboration.

S1 stated, "*Solar is a recent product; bulk volumes of waste will only emerge after 15–20 years,*" highlighting the timeline of waste. **S3** emphasized the potential for India's role in recycling, saying, "*India can become the world's biggest recycler with better regulation and investment.*" They further added, "*Circularity of materials will improve as recycling infrastructure and regulations stabilize.*" As evidenced by European models where funds from recovered materials support the financial sustainability of recycling programs, market formation can balance operating expenses and enhance profitability (Radavičius et al., 2021).

The growth of the solar energy market was highlighted by multiple stakeholders. Both **S4** and **S5** mentioned, "*The solar energy market, particularly in India, has unfolded very well, and you can say a lot of capacity addition happening every year.*" **S4** noted, "*The growth rate has been exponential, particularly after the introduction of net metering policies and subsidies.*" Both stakeholders also referred to the PM Surya Yojana, with **S5** saying, "*It is helping provide clarity and uniformity to the solar energy market.*"

Infrastructure development and localized solutions were identified as key focus areas. **S6** remarked, "*Infrastructure development and capacity building are initially required for recycling.*" They also highlighted, "*Stricter regulations and specific implementation are required for solar waste management.*"

The need for improved policies and frameworks was a recurring theme. Both **S5** and **S6** emphasized, "*A centralized regulatory framework is needed to streamline solar waste management across states.*" **S5** stated, "*Proper R&D support and investment are critical for creating efficient recycling technologies.*" **S6** said, "*Battery energy storage systems are coming into the picture.*"

Panel discussions held throughout the event also emphasized the significance of coordinating infrastructure development with regulatory frameworks. Speakers pointed to the success of the European Union's WEEE Directive as an illustration of how legislation might encourage investment in recycling infrastructure.

Technology and innovation were frequently mentioned as game-changers. **S5** talked about how *"IoT and remote monitoring could track performance and life cycle of solar panels."* They also highlighted advancements like *"smart monitoring, RFID tags, and automated systems,"* which they believe would *"improve recycling efficiency."*

Local manufacturing and reducing dependency on imports were also addressed. **S4** stated, *"India needs to develop its own infrastructure and quality standards to reduce dependency on imports."* They added, *"Promoting local manufacturing and balancing costs with quality is critical for growth,"* and noted, *"Big players should lead the way in infrastructure development to encourage smaller players to follow."* **S6** observed, *"Indian modules are being used in utility-scale projects, which is a good thing that we are producing and utilizing locally."*

Education and awareness were also mentioned as essential. **S5** said, *"Educating B2B and B2C customers on end-of-life management is key to promoting sustainability."*

4.2 Unique Themes

4.2.1 Role of Design in Solar Panel Circularity

Stakeholders shared their ideas and thoughts on how the design of solar panels plays a key role in waste management and recycling. **S4** pointed out, *"The design hasn't changed much in recent years, but efficiency improvements have increased output."*

S3 explained, *"If you can keep components separate in your design, waste management becomes easier."* At the same time, they pointed out challenges of different solar panels in the market by saying, *"Different companies using different material compositions make waste management challenging."* They also highlighted the problems with complexity of solar recycling: *"The solar cell is a complex product with various materials embedded, making recycling challenging."* This aligns with the findings of Radavičius et al. (2021), who noted similar issues in the European market, where closely tied structures and multi-layered designs challenge the recovery of materials.

Durability in design was another issue that was discussed. **S3** mentioned, "*Durability can sometimes compromise recyclability, such as the use of adhesives instead of screws,*" which makes panels harder to take apart. They also talked about the differences between panel types, noting, "*Thin film solar panels are more recyclable but less durable compared to polycrystalline panels.*"

The layered structure of solar panels was described as another obstacle. **S4** agreed with the issues of solar panel design as, "*Solar panel is like a sandwich, you know, and there is plastic*". Also, a plastic layer inside the solar panel which is very difficult to extract in solar cells." This makes the recycling process even more complicated.

There were some ideas for improving how panels are managed throughout their lifecycle. **S4** suggested, "*RFID tags can track solar panels throughout their lifecycle, improving traceability.*"

4.2.2 Role of operations and maintenance in Circularity

Stakeholders shared their thoughts on how operations and maintenance play a crucial role in ensuring the longevity and circularity of solar panels. **S1** said, "*The structure should be so steady that there should not be any play or any movement in the structure at the time of winds*" emphasizing the importance of a strong and stable design. They also pointed out that "*the workmanship and the craftsmanship of installation are just as important as the structure material,*" highlighting the role of proper installation in preventing long-term issues.

For maintenance, **S1** shared an insight, saying, "*If you can get your module cleaned, solar panel cleaned, then only go for solar*". They also brought up the role of technology, stating, "*Right now, all our projects are Internet-connected, and we keep track of generation through apps.*" The use of Internet of Things (IoT) technology helps monitor energy output, which, as **S1** explained, "*enables monitoring of annual and daily generation, improving the lifespan of the system.*"

Automation is becoming increasingly important, too. **S6** explained, "*Robotics in installation and recycling can reduce errors and mishandling,*" pointing to its potential in minimizing waste and improving precision. They also supported the idea of IoT integration, agreeing that "*IoT and remote monitoring could track performance and life cycle of solar panels.*"

Chapter 5 Discussion

The rapid growth of the solar energy sector, particularly in developing nations like India, underscores the dual challenges of scaling energy systems while addressing the environmental implications of solar panel waste (Singh & Gupta, 2020; Sharma et al., 2021; Hydrogen Fuel News, 2017). Although celebrated for their emission-free energy generation, solar photovoltaic (PV) panels present significant waste challenges due to their complex material composition and the lack of established recycling infrastructure (IEA, 2022). This study critically examines these challenges within India's extended producer responsibility (EPR) policy framework, focusing on stakeholder perspectives and systemic gaps in collection, recovery, and recycling processes.

The results chapter reveals a multifaceted problem, including design inefficiencies, low stakeholder cohesion, logistical hurdles, and insufficient economic incentives. At the same time, it identifies opportunities for improvement through design innovations, policy reform, and strategic stakeholder integration. This discussion connects these findings to broader debates in sustainability, waste management, and circular economy principles, addressing the research questions and exploring pathways for enhancing solar waste management in India.

Research Question 1: How can design innovations and material choices improve the environmental sustainability of solar panels under India's EPR framework?

Most stakeholders highlighted that current solar panel designs significantly hinder disassembly and recycling efforts, particularly adhesives and layered material composition.

Sandwich structure

Durability and recyclability often conflict in current solar panel designs (Huang, Atasu and Toktay, 2019). Although thin-film panels are more recyclable than polycrystalline panels, the lack of an aluminium frame makes them less durable and unsuitable for India's harsh climate, making polycrystalline panels the dominant choice. However, they are often designed with minimal regard for recyclability. Stakeholders such as S4 emphasized that

while solar panel efficiency has improved, fundamental design principles have not evolved to incorporate sustainability. Performance precedes recyclability, indicating a discrepancy between design and EPR goals. Also, While Solar PV efficiency has improved over the years, with increased watt peak outputs, S4 noted that the fundamental design of panels has remained unchanged. This reflects a tension in solar manufacturing: optimizing performance vs. ensuring sustainability (Hydrogen Fuel News, 2017).

Monitoring

A further significant issue is the absence of adequate labelling and traceability systems. Stakeholders recommended using RFID and NFC tags to track solar panels over time. These technologies, which are currently gaining traction in Europe under frameworks like the WEEE Directive, enable real-time monitoring and compliance with recycling targets (WEEE Forum, 2021). Implementing such systems in India could improve accountability and facilitate coordination between producers, recyclers, and authorities. However, stakeholders argue that the high implementation costs of these technologies continue to be a significant barrier in India's price-sensitive solar industry.

The Role of IoT and Lifecycle Management

Technological innovations like IoT-enabled devices have the potential to significantly extend the life of solar panels and improve recycling efficiency. S1 claims IoT-based predictive maintenance can detect issues early, preventing major malfunctions and extending the panels' usable life. IoT-driven lifecycle management systems also offer real-time data on panel health and end-of-life status, speeding up recycling schedules. IoT-enabled systems boost productivity by tracking material flows and reducing operational delays (Kayalvizhi et al. (2024).

Opportunities in India's Expanding Solar Manufacturing Sector

India's expanding solar manufacturing sector, with leading companies like Vikram, solar, Adani and Waaree Energies, presents an opportunity to incorporate circular design principles in solar manufacturing, especially with the promotion of the Make in India campaign for Solar cells to reduce reliance on Chinese modules (Sethuraman, 2024). As the country prepares to implement EPR policies, programmes should be designed to incentivise Producers to incorporate changes upstream at the design phase (European Commission, 2007).

Current regulations, such as the requirement to store EOL panels until 2034, fail to address the urgent need for design and recycling innovations. Mandatory buyback programs may encourage design advancements upstream and guarantee that manufacturers are held accountable for end-of-life management. This emphasizes the need to coordinate regulatory efforts with beneficial design improvements, as observed in cases where EPR frameworks promote modularity and recyclability (EU-INDIA: TCP, 2021; PerfectID, no date).

To incentivise producers to adopt sustainable practices, regulatory agencies should implement differentiated EPR pricing. This approach promotes the use of recyclable materials and modular designs, which facilitate recycling and repair while discouraging wasteful or environmentally harmful production methods (WEEE Forum, 2021).

While worldwide breakthroughs in IoT and recycling infrastructure provide important models, stakeholders emphasised the need to customise these solutions to India's industrial and socioeconomic situations. For example, achieving circularity in India's solar industry requires increasing material separability and reducing the use of adhesives. Financial incentives, such as tax exemptions or subsidies, for using modular designs are shown to be crucial for fostering compliance with the EPR framework as agreed by the stakeholders.

By aligning innovations with international PV waste management standards, India can reduce adhesive use, enhance material separability, and leverage IoT-based lifecycle management.

Research Question 2: What insights can be gained from semi-structured interviews with Solar PV stakeholders to improve collaboration and address challenges in collection and recovery?

The semi-structured interviews revealed important challenges and opportunities for multilevel stakeholder collaboration to enhance solar PV waste collection and recovery. Stakeholders like S1 expressed concerns about the logistical and financial difficulties of complying with EPR regulations, citing unclear standards and a lack of adequate take-back infrastructure as significant roadblocks.

Fragmented collaboration

According to the interviewees, one of the biggest challenges was the stakeholders' fragmented cooperation. S3 noted that collaboration between manufacturers and recyclers could encourage eco-friendly designs and more equitably distribute logistical costs. However, these efforts remain unrealized due to insufficient funding and legislative support.

The lack of awareness among stakeholders exacerbates these challenges. Most stakeholders admitted that they did not completely understand their EPR responsibilities, particularly about decommissioning solar PV systems. Effective end-of-life management is hampered by this ignorance, highlighting the need for capacity-building initiatives (Divya et al., 2021). The informal sector, which is essential to decentralized waste collection, is also impacted by systemic neglect. Despite their importance, informal waste pickers often lack the tools and training to handle hazardous chemicals safely as discussed by S4.

Integration of the Informal Sector

Integrating unorganized enterprises into formal recycling systems might close these gaps while boosting productivity and reducing environmental risks. S3 suggested financial incentives and capacity-building programs to formally recognize waste pickers' efforts and encourage their collaboration with formal stakeholders. However, no institutional institutions are currently in place to promote this integration, as Chaturvedi (2022) mentions. Producer Responsibility Organisations (PROs) are regulated by EPR frameworks, link producers, recyclers, and collection networks. According to studies like EU TCP (2021) and CSTEP (2023), they are essential in achieving material recovery goals because they facilitate information exchange, coordinate actions, and ensure compliance through centralised tracking systems. But lack of defined targets and incentives for PRO's restrict them to fully realise their potential in advancing the goals of the circular economy (EU-TCP, 2021).

Public Awareness and Engagement

Public awareness and education emerged as essential components for fostering collaboration. S2 recommended educating the public about proper recycling practices and promoting participation in EPR frameworks through community radio, local media, and educational institutions. Survey done by Nain and Kumar, (2020) revealed that consumers are willing to pay for recycling initiatives as the public has trust in the PV tech and the green integrity should be maintained (Rutkowska, Bartoszczuk and Singh, 2021).

Thus, Stakeholders emphasized the necessity of a coordinated system to boost waste collection and promote collaboration between producers and informal collectors (Sica et al., 2018). These centralized strategies must also consider India's diverse socioeconomic and

geographical landscape. Decentralized solutions, for example, are required in India due to the country's unique logistical difficulties in rural and remote locations, even though centralized systems operate effectively in Germany (Michael and Iyer, 2022).

Research Question 3: What policy adjustments and infrastructure enhancements are necessary to optimize solar panel waste management while supporting circular economy principles?

India's EPR framework for solar PV waste management faces significant barriers that keep it from aligning with circular economy principles. The analysis highlighted critical inadequacies, including inadequate infrastructure for recycling, inadequate means for collecting, and logistical inefficiencies.

Gaps in India's EPR Framework

S2 emphasized the absence of infrastructure for segregation and collection in certain areas, mainly rural and hilly areas. At the same time, S1 and S6 identified transportation costs as a barrier in certain situations when the value of damaged panels does not justify the expense. These challenges underscore the need for a targeted approach to infrastructure development and policy alignment.

Cluster-Based Solutions for Recycling

The Karnataka study of the CSTEP cluster-based framework offers a scalable and context-sensitive solution. By setting up collecting and recycling facilities in regions with large densities of solar systems, the idea allows for localized material recovery while lowering transportation costs and distances. Cluster-based centres, which act as processing hubs for critical materials like glass, aluminium, and plastics, significantly boost recovery efficiency. Stakeholders supported the inclusion of unauthorized recyclers in these hubs to ensure safety and compliance with EPR standards, emphasizing the need for formal training and clearly defined responsibilities. This dual technique simultaneously addresses inclusivity and scalability (CSTEP, 2023).

Policy Integration with Circular Economy

The results demonstrated that logistical challenges present a significant barrier to effective waste management. Stakeholders did not emphasize these challenges equally, but there was consensus that solutions like decentralized collecting hubs could alleviate some logistical inefficiencies. South Korea's decentralized e-waste collection centres exemplify how such systems can enhance recovery rates while lowering costs (Kim and Park, 2018). Additionally, Germany's progressive implementation of the WEEE Directive and its regional infrastructure illustrate how gradual recycling limits can help stakeholders adapt over time (UmweltBundesamt, 2019). These examples support the feasibility of India's cluster-based approach within a cohesive national framework.

Leveraging Global Best Practices

The results also highlighted the urgent need for policy changes to enhance waste management systems. Stakeholders proposed gradually introducing recycling targets to match the growth of infrastructure and market conditions. This strategy is similar to what has been practised in countries like Germany and Japan, where waste management systems progressed through incremental goals and infrastructure investments (Hosoda, 2006). Additionally, it was stressed that manufacturing licenses and bidding processes should incorporate compliance with Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) standards to promote accountability and collaboration among various stakeholders.

Various stakeholders identified the need to address transportation inefficiencies as a particular challenge. Specifically, S2, S3, and S6 pointed out the practical difficulties of waste disposal in remote regions, where high transportation costs remain a significant barrier. These findings underscore the importance of developing regionally tailored solutions considering India's diverse topography and infrastructure. The need for standard regulations to ensure state-by-state compliance with EPR requirements was also recognized. Stakeholders underlined the importance of a centralized regulatory structure to guarantee consistent enforcement while accommodating decentralized systems for region-specific challenges. Coordination between state and federal initiatives is necessary to ensure the efficacy of decentralized systems within a cohesive policy framework and to minimize fragmentation.

Research Question 4: How can business models and economic incentives make solar panel waste management profitable, scalable, and aligned with circular economy principles?

The results emphasise the need for innovative financial incentives and sustainable business models that address systemic inefficiencies and advance the circular economy concepts to ensure profitability and scalability in India's solar PV waste management. Stakeholders identified several financial challenges, such as low material recovery values, high operational and shipping costs, and a lack of robust markets for recovered resources.

Cost-Sharing Mechanisms

Implementing cost-sharing schemes is one way to distribute financial responsibility among stakeholders. S2 suggested incorporating EPR compliance expenses into existing solar subsidy programs to alleviate the strain on smaller producers and recyclers. This would increase the viability of compliance without compromising profits. Stakeholders also underlined how manufacturers may be encouraged to utilise modular and recyclable designs by differing EPR costs, aligning product development with end-of-life issues (European Commission, 2011).

Obligatory buyback programs are important to material recovery as these initiatives can stabilise material flow and lessen dependency on unofficial channels by ensuring that producers bear responsibility for the returns of solar panels at the end of their life cycle. Japan's Home Appliance Recycling Law served as their model (Hosoda, 2006; METI, 2021). Stakeholders emphasised incorporating financial incentives, such as consumer refunds or discounts on new installations, to increase customer involvement and create a steady material supply.

Decentralized Recycling Hubs and Infrastructure

According to the interviews, decentralised recycling hubs are an evident solution to logistical inefficiencies, particularly when integrated into the CSTEP cluster-based paradigm. The deliberate placement of these hubs in regions with a high concentration of solar panels reduces transportation costs and improves accessibility. Stakeholders supported the inclusion of informal recyclers in these sites so they might benefit from their existing experience. Proper training and financial incentives for employees in the unorganised sector would ensure safety and compliance and reduce operating expenses (CSTEP, 2023). This relationship enables managing waste effectively even in locations with limited resources by enhancing inclusivity and scalability.

Low waste volumes must be addressed in the early stages of EPR deployment. Providing specific financial incentives to waste collectors and classifying collection requests based on regional waste generation trends were proposed as workable substitutes. These actions could help close gaps in material availability, especially in areas with low solar installations.

Developing Secondary Markets

The results also identified the absence of strong secondary markets for recovered materials as a significant economic obstacle. Markets for silicon, glass, and rare metals can be established to stabilise demand and ensure that recovered commodities generate revenue for recyclers. Thus, creating demand for recycled materials might aid in closing the loop and promoting the concepts of the circular economy in India's growing solar manufacturing sector.

Technological Integration and Innovation

Technology is crucial for improving efficiency and cost-effectiveness. The results show that tracking technologies enabled by RFID and IoT are critical to monitoring solar panel lifecycle and traceability (PerfectID, n.d.; WEEE Forum, 2021). AI-powered sorting technologies, which stakeholders have called revolutionary, enable recycling systems to function successfully on a wide scale by reducing workforce costs and increasing material recovery rates (Kayalvizhi et al., 2024). Stakeholders recommended particular government subsidies or tax incentives to speed up the adoption of these technologies, particularly in the early phases of EPR deployment.

Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs)

The results also mentioned public-private partnerships (PPPs) as a means of encouraging innovation and sharing costs. Stakeholders pointed to Jamshedpur's successful e-waste management program as an example of how PPPs may assist regional systems while providing access to state-of-the-art recycling technologies (Michael and Iyer, 2022). PPPs may attract private sector investment, promote the development of decentralised hubs for solar PV waste, and ensure sustainability in the long run.

Regulatory incentives

Regulations like landfill fees and fines for noncompliance were successful ways to deter improper disposal in many European countries (EU-TCP, 2021). Global approaches, such as Germany's centralized EPR framework system under the WEEE Directive, which rely on financial incentives to ensure compliance, can provide valuable information (IEA-PVPS,

2024). Stakeholders agreed that when paired with clear and legally binding EPR requirements, these actions could promote the use of authorized gathering techniques and reduce reliance on unsustainable practices.

Chapter 6: Conclusion and Recommendations

This study critically examined the systemic potential and constraints in India's solar PV waste management practices using the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) paradigm. Ineffective panel design, logistical constraints, poor recycling infrastructure, and a lack of financial incentives were significant barriers to waste management programs' sustainability and scalability. Design complexity, such as the use of adhesives and multi-layered materials, presents significant barriers to recyclability, while practical concerns, especially in remote and rural areas, raise costs and reduce collection efficiency.

Despite these challenges, the study found promising opportunities to improve solar waste management in India. Decentralised recycling facilities are a practical solution to logistical challenges. By focusing on areas with a high density of solar panels, these hubs might provide localised waste material processing and reduce transportation costs. The cluster-based approach, stressed in CSTEP's model, offers valuable insights into how these hubs could function effectively by focussing on localised processing and reducing transportation expenses. These techniques demonstrated the importance of tailoring solutions to India's diverse socioeconomic and geographic conditions. It was also concluded that incorporating informal recyclers into formal systems was an essential opportunity to capitalise on their experience through structured training programs and monetary incentives to guarantee compliance and safety.

Economic strategies such as mandatory buyback programs and variable EPR charges are critical for stabilising material recovery flows and incentivising businesses to adopt recyclable designs. When combined with the development of robust secondary markets for recovered commodities like silicon and glass, these actions could significantly improve the financial sustainability of recycling operations. However, the survey also noted that economic viability requires long-term planning and collaboration between local recyclers, industry stakeholders, and lawmakers.

Technologies including RFID tags, IoT-enabled tracking systems, and AI-driven sorting have the potential to maximise material recovery, reduce personnel costs, and improve compliance with EPR laws. Success requires cooperation from all parties involved, and public-private partnerships (PPPs) are vital for funding infrastructure, promoting innovation, and bridging gaps in underserved communities. Customised consumer awareness advertisements that consider India's cultural diversity are essential to raising public participation in recycling initiatives.

The results emphasise the necessity of government efforts to link solar PV waste management with the ideas of the circular economy. These efforts include setting recycling targets, developing regulations unique to specific regions, and incorporating compliance into licensing and tendering processes. India can develop a solar waste management system that is equitable, sustainable, and scalable by employing a thorough and inclusive strategy that blends multi-stakeholder collaboration, financial incentives, and technological innovation.

This report offers valuable insights into solar waste management in developing countries and practical recommendations for regulators, industry stakeholders, and researchers. By addressing the structural flaws identified in this report, India may become a global leader in sustainable energy practices, achieve environmental sustainability, and create economic opportunities.

6.1. Assumptions and limitations of the study

This study's methodology and analysis were based on several assumptions. The conclusions drawn from the six semi-structured stakeholder interviews reflect the broader opportunities and issues in India's solar PV waste management ecosystem. Additionally, it assumes that the secondary literature and papers under study accurately portray the state of solar waste management in India and beyond today. Furthermore, the study assumes that issues like poor recycling infrastructure, inefficient logistics, and a lack of appropriate financial incentives exist in all contexts and regions. India's industrial and economic framework can accommodate new technologies like IoT-enabled tracking and AI-powered sorting. Lastly, the study assumes that India's regulatory framework will continue evolving and addressing the identified gaps, particularly under the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) policy.

However, the study had several limitations. Due to time constraints, only six interviews were done, which might not entirely reflect the variety of perspectives in India's solar PV ecosystem, particularly among informal recyclers and grassroots players. Even though secondary data provided helpful background, the lack of interviews with informal recyclers may have limited the depth of insights into their particular problems and potential contributions. The geographic focus on a few selected locations may have caused disparities in solar waste management practices and infrastructure in other regions of the country to go unnoticed.

Another disadvantage is using secondary data to evaluate technological and economic feasibility; this data may not adequately reflect the state of the market or the pace of technological advancement. Furthermore, because of the rapidly evolving regulatory environment, some recommendations must be adjusted to comply with impending policy changes.

Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable guidance and highlights significant opportunities to improve solar PV waste management in India. It emphasises sustainable and scalable solutions that align with the principles of the circular economy and can adapt to the sector's evolving needs.

Future research should examine economic feasibility studies to assess the cost-effectiveness and scalability of advanced recycling technologies and distributed recycling hubs. Understanding consumer behaviour, particularly their dedication to recycling and readiness to participate in buyback programs, is essential for creating effective policy interventions. Incorporating informal recyclers into formal systems requires further research, particularly in developing financial and legal frameworks that capitalise on their expertise and ensure safety and compliance.

Further investigation into technological developments, especially the long-term effects of blockchain, IoT, and AI, is necessary to enhance operational scalability and efficiency. Research should also concentrate on creating economical and efficient disassembly techniques for adhesive-heavy panel designs to address major obstacles to recycling. Comparative life cycle assessments of recycled vs. virgin materials are essential to provide solid data for policy advocacy and bolster the case for improved recycling procedures.

Reference List

1. Ali, A. *et al.* (2024) 'Solar photovoltaic module end-of-life waste management regulations: International practices and implications for the kingdom of Saudi Arabia', *Sustainability*, 16(16), p. 7215. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16167215>.
2. American Progress (2024) *First Solar Thin Film Research and Development Center*, *Americanprogress.org*. Available at: <https://www.americanprogress.org/article/first-solar-thin-film-research-and-development-center/> (Accessed: 9 December 2024).
3. Arora (2018) *Greening the solar PV value chain*, *Teriin.org*. Available at: <https://www.teriin.org/sites/default/files/2018-10/greening-solar-PV-value-chain.pdf> (Accessed: 14 December 2024).
4. AstuteAnalytica India Pvt. Ltd. (2024) *India e-waste management market to offer opportunity worth USD 5,198.52 million by 2032*, *AstuteAnalytica India Pvt. Ltd.* Available at: <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2024/03/25/2851808/0/en/India-e-Waste-Management-Market-to-Offer-Opportunity-Worth-USD-5-198-52-Million-by-2032-Metals-are-A-Hidden-Treasure-Trove-Says-Astute-Analytica.html> (Accessed: 6 December 2024).
5. Baldé, C.P. *et al.* (2017) *The Global E-waste Monitor 2017: Quantities, Flows, and Resources*. United Nations University, International Telecommunication Union, and International Solid Waste Association.
6. Bellini, E. (2020) *South Korea to introduce new rules for PV recycling*, *PV magazine International*. Available at: <https://www.PV-magazine.com/2020/10/08/south-korea-to-introduce-new-rules-for-PV-recycling/> (Accessed: 15 December 2024).
7. Boyatzis, R.E. (1998) *Transforming qualitative information: Thematic analysis and code development*. Sage.
8. Center for Study of Science, Technology and Policy (2023) *Addressing the Impending crisis of Solar Photovoltaic waste in India*, *Cstep.in*. Available at: https://cstep.in/drupal/sites/default/files/2023-08/Addressing%20the%20impending%20crisis%20of%20solar%20photovoltaic%20waste%20in%20India%20A%20comprehensive%20recycling%20framework%20with%20policy%20solutions_0.pdf (Accessed: 17 December 2024).
9. Chaturvedi (2022) *Implications of a Net-Zero Target for India's Sectoral Energy Transitions and Climate Policy*, *Ceew.in*. Available at: <https://www.ceew.in/publications/implications-net-zero-target-indias-sectoral-energy-transition-s-and-climate-policy> (Accessed: 6 December 2024).

10. Chowdhury, M.F. (2014) 'Interpretivism in aiding our understanding of the contemporary social world', *Open journal of philosophy*, 04(03), pp. 432–438. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojpp.2014.43047>.
11. Chowdhury, M.S. *et al.* (2020) 'An overview of solar photovoltaic panels' end-of-life material recycling', *Energy strategy reviews*, 27(100431), p. 100431. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2019.100431>.
12. Choy, L.T. and Faculty of Arts and Social Science, University of Malaya, Malaysia (2014) 'The strengths and weaknesses of research methodology: Comparison and complimentary between qualitative and quantitative approaches', *IOSR journal of humanities and social science*, 19(4), pp. 99–104. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.9790/0837-194399104>.
13. *Circular economy* (no date) *Irena.org*. Available at: <https://www.irena.org/Energy-Transition/Policy/Circular-economy> (Accessed: 9 December 2024).
14. Delhi Bureau (2024) *Robust recycling of increasing solar waste critical for India's energy security: CEEW, Krishak Jagat*. Available at: <https://www.en.krishakjagat.org/india-region/robust-recycling-of-increasing-solar-waste-critical-for-indias-energy-security-ceew/> (Accessed: 2 January 2025).
15. Divya, A. *et al.* (2021) 'Review on recycling of solar modules/panels', *Solar energy materials and solar cells: an international journal devoted to photovoltaic, photothermal, and photochemical solar energy conversion*, 253(112151), p. 112151. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2022.112151>.
16. Dwivedy, M., Suchde, P. and Mittal, R.K. (2015) 'Modeling and assessment of e-waste take-back strategies in India', *Resources, conservation, and recycling*, 96, pp. 11–18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2015.01.003>.
17. Einhaus, R. *et al.* (2018) 'Recycling and Reuse potential of NICE PV-Modules', in *2018 IEEE 7th World Conference on Photovoltaic Energy Conversion (WCPEC) (A Joint Conference of 45th IEEE PVSC, 28th PVSEC & 34th EU PVSEC)*. IEEE, pp. 561–564.
18. EU-INDIA:TCP (2021) *PV waste management in India: comparative analysis of the state of play and recommendations 2021*, *Cecp-eu.in*. Available at: <https://www.cecp-eu.in/uploads/documents/events/PV-waste-management-report-25-01-2021.pdf> (Accessed: 5 December 2024).
19. European Commission (2007) *The Producer Responsibility Principle of the WEEE Directive*, *Europa.eu*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/environment/pdf/waste/weee/final_rep_okopol.pdf (Accessed: 3 January 2025).
20. European Commission (2011) *MANAGEMENT PLAN 2011 DG ENVIRONMENT*, *Europa.eu*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/dgs/environment/pdf/management_plan_2011.pdf (Accessed: 7 December 2024).
21. European Commission (2019) *Europe's greener photovoltaic value chain*, *CORDIS | European Commission*. Publication Office/CORDIS. Available at:

- <https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/258269-europes-greener-photovoltaic-value-chain>
(Accessed: 14 December 2024).
22. Firstsolar (2022) *Global Recycling Program*, *Firstsolar.com*. Available at:
<https://www.firstsolar.com/Solutions/Recycling> (Accessed: 8 January 2025).
 23. Fthenakis, V.M. and Wang, W. (2020) *Life cycle and end-of-life management of solar panels: Environmental impacts and opportunities*. *Progress in Photovoltaics*.
 24. Gautam & Ayush (2021) *End-of-life solar photovoltaic e-waste assessment in India: a step towards a circular economy*, *Scopus.com*. Available at:
<https://www.scopus.com/record/display.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85091761849&origin=inward>
(Accessed: 11 December 2024).
 25. Government of India (2022) *India's Updated First Nationally Determined Contribution Under Paris Agreement*, *Unfccc.int*. Available at:
<https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2022-08/India%20Updated%20First%20Nationally%20Determined%20Contrib.pdf#page=3> (Accessed: 16 December 2024).
 26. Hosoda, E. (2006) *Japan's home appliance recycling law*, *Env.go.jp*. Available at:
https://www.env.go.jp/recycle//3r/en/asia/02_03-4/06.pdf?utm_source=chatgpt.com
(Accessed: 3 January 2025).
 27. Huang, X. (natalie), Atasu, A. and Toktay, L.B. (2019) 'Design implications of extended producer responsibility for durable products', *Management science*, 65(6), pp. 2573–2590. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.2018.3072>.
 28. Hydrogen Fuel News (2017) *Solar Energy Capacity Archives*, *Hydrogenfuelnews.com*. Available at: <https://www.hydrogenfuelnews.com/tag/solar-energy-capacity/> (Accessed: 2 January 2025).
 29. IEA (2016) 'End-of-Life Management: Solar Photovoltaic Panels', *IEA* [Preprint].
 30. IEA (2022) *Special Report on Solar PV Global Supply Chains*, *IEA*. Available at:
<https://www.iea.org/reports/solar-PV-global-supply-chains/executive-summary> (Accessed: 7 December 2024).
 31. Iea-PVps (2022) *Status of PV Module Recycling in Selected IEA PVPS Task12 Countries 2022*, *Iea-PVps.org*. Available at:
https://iea-PVps.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/Report-IEA-PVPS-T12-24_2022_Status-of-PV-Module-Recycling.pdf?utm_s (Accessed: 17 December 2024).
 32. Iea-PVps (2024) *Status of PV Module Take-Back and Recycling in Germany 2024*, *Iea-PVps.org*. Available at:
<https://iea-PVps.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/IEA-PVPS-T12-27-Report-PV-Recycling-in-Germany.pdf> (Accessed: 15 December 2024).
 33. Jain, S., Sharma, T. and Gupta, A.K. (2022) 'End-of-life management of solar PV waste in India: Situation analysis and proposed policy framework', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 153(111774), p. 111774. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111774>.

34. Kabir, S.E. *et al.* (2023) 'Adoption and implementation of extended producer responsibility for sustainable management of end-of-life solar photovoltaic panels'. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.22034/GJESM.2023.09.SI.15>.
35. Kayalvizhi, N. *et al.* (2024) 'IoT-enabled real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance for solar systems: Maximizing efficiency and minimizing downtime', in *2024 International Conference on Smart Systems for applications in Electrical Sciences (ICSSES)*. IEEE, pp. 1–5.
36. Kim, H. and Park, H. (2018) 'PV waste management at the Crossroads of circular economy and energy transition: The case of South Korea', *Sustainability*, 10(10), p. 3565. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10103565>.
37. Kim, S. *et al.* (2024) 'Development of eco-friendly pretreatment processes for high-purity silicon recovery from end-of-life photovoltaic modules', *RSC advances*, 14(43), pp. 31451–31460. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1039/d4ra04878d>.
38. Ko, J. *et al.* (2023) 'Review on separation processes of end-of-life silicon photovoltaic modules', *Energies*, 16(11), p. 4327. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16114327>.
39. Komoto, K. and Lee, J.-S. (2018) *End-of-Life Management of Photovoltaic Panels: Trends in PV Module Recycling Technologies*. Paris.
40. Köntges (2014) *Review of Failures of Photovoltaic Modules*, *iea-PVps.org*. Available at: https://iea-PVps.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/IEA-PVPS_T13-01_2014_Review_of_Failures_of_Photovoltaic_Modules_Final.pdf (Accessed: 6 December 2024).
41. Kumar, P. and Sharma, A. (2021) '*Circular Economy and E-waste Regulations in India: A Critical Analysis*', *Critical Analysis*. Environmental Science and Policy*, 114, pp. 152–160
42. Latunussa, C.E.L. *et al.* (2016) 'Life Cycle Assessment of an innovative recycling process for crystalline silicon photovoltaic panels', *Solar energy materials and solar cells: an international journal devoted to photovoltaic, photothermal, and photochemical solar energy conversion*, 156, pp. 101–111. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2016.03.020>.
43. Lunardi, M.M. *et al.* (2018) 'A review of recycling processes for photovoltaic modules', in B. Zaidi (ed.) *Solar Panels and Photovoltaic Materials*. London: InTech.
44. Maani, T. *et al.* (2020) 'Environmental impacts of recycling crystalline silicon (c-Si) and cadmium telluride (CDTE) solar panels', *The Science of the total environment*, 735(138827), p. 138827. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138827>.
45. Malandrino, O. *et al.* (2017) 'Policies and measures for sustainable management of solar panel end-of-life in Italy', *Sustainability*, 9(4), p. 481. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9040481>.
46. METI (2021) *Act on Recycling of Specified Home Appliances*, *Meti.go.jp*. Available at: https://www.meti.go.jp/policy/recycle/main/english/law/home.html?utm_source=chatgpt.com (Accessed: 3 January 2025).
47. Michael, J. and Iyer, A. (2022) *Cleanest Cities of India: Jamshedpur, the industrial city, manages its e-waste*, *Down To Earth*. Available at:

- https://www.downtoearth.org.in/waste/cleanest-cities-of-india-jamshedpur-the-industrial-city-manages-its-e-waste-81560?utm_source=chatgpt.com (Accessed: 3 January 2025).
48. Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change (2022) *E-Waste (Management) Rules, 2022*, *Nic.in*. Available at:
https://cpcb.nic.in/uploads/Projects/E-Waste/e-waste_rules_2022.pdf (Accessed: 8 January 2025).
49. Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India (2023) *National Statement by Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi at COP26 Summit in Glasgow, Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India*. Available at:
<https://www.mea.gov.in/Speeches-Statements.htm?dtl/34466/National+Statement+by+Prime+Minister+Shri+Narendra+Modi+at+COP26+Summit+in+Glasgow> (Accessed: 16 December 2024).
50. Ministry of new and renewable energy (2023) *Solar overview*, *Gov.in*. Available at:
<https://mnre.gov.in/en/solar-overview/> (Accessed: 6 December 2024).
51. MNRE (2020) *Solar grid connected*, *Gov.in*. Available at:
<https://mnre.gov.in/en/solar-grid-connected/> (Accessed: 6 December 2024).
52. MoEF&CC (2016) *Hazardous Waste Management Rules*, *Nic.in*. Available at:
<https://cpcb.nic.in/rules/> (Accessed: 11 December 2024).
53. Monier (2014) *Development of Guidance on Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR)*, *Europa.eu*. Available at:
https://ec.europa.eu/environment/pdf/waste/target_review/Guidance%20on%20EPR%20-%20Final%20Report.pdf (Accessed: 5 December 2024).
54. *NASA science* (2017) *Nasa.gov*. Available at: <https://science.nasa.gov/sun/facts/> (Accessed: 5 December 2024).
55. Nasir, Z. (2024) *Rethinking waste: A circular economy approach to sustainable business*, *Circular Computing*. Available at:
<https://circularcomputing.com/news/rethinking-waste-a-circular-economy-approach/> (Accessed: 3 January 2025).
56. O., J., M., O.C. and N., J. (2007) *Heavy metal pollution and human biotoxic effects*, *Academicjournals.org*. Available at:
https://academicjournals.org/article/article1380209337_Duruibe%20et%20al.pdf?hop=undefined (Accessed: 7 December 2024).
57. OECD (2001) *Extended producer Responsibility: A GUIDANCE MANUAL FOR GOVERNMENTS*, *Oecd-ilibrary.org*. Available at:
<https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/docserver/9789264189867-en.pdf?expires=1734282949&id=id&accname=guest&checksum=A4F4BD728C02847C00466534371D90D8> (Accessed: 15 December 2024).
58. Orosz, T. *et al.* (2024) 'Current challenges in operation, performance, and maintenance of photovoltaic panels', *Energies*, 17(6), p. 1306. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.3390/en17061306>.

59. Perfectid (n.d.) *Revolutionizing Solar Energy: RFID Solar Tags by PerfectID for Precision Tracking*, Perfectid.com. Available at: <https://www.perfectid.com> (Accessed: 2 January 2025).
60. PIB (2023a) *Solar Waste treatment under E-Waste (Management) rules, 2022*, Gov.in. Available at: <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleaselframePage.aspx?PRID=1906920> (Accessed: 6 December 2024).
61. PIB (2023b) *Steps to address issue of solar waste*, Gov.in. Available at: <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleaselframePage.aspx?PRID=1989819> (Accessed: 8 January 2025).
62. Radavičius, T. et al. (2021) 'Circular solar industry supply chain through product technological design changes', *Insights into Regional Development* [Preprint]. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.9770/ird.2021.3.3\(1\)](https://doi.org/10.9770/ird.2021.3.3(1)).
63. Rai, S. (2021) '*Circular economy for solar PV waste: Opportunities and challenges', *Journal of Environmental Management*, 280.
64. Rathore, N. and Panwar, N.L. (2022) 'Strategic overview of management of future solar photovoltaic panel waste generation in the Indian context', *Waste management & research: the journal of the International Solid Wastes and Public Cleansing Association, ISWA*, 40(5), pp. 504–518. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242x211003977>.
65. Rossi & Solarpower Europe (2024) *Demystifying upcoming EU Ecodesign and Energy Label rules for solar PV*, *PV magazine International*. Available at: <https://www.PV-magazine.com/2024/02/20/demystifying-upcoming-eu-ecodesign-and-energy-label-rules-for-solar-PV/> (Accessed: 15 December 2024).
66. Roy, M., Jha, M.K. and Bhattacharya, S. (2024) 'Challenges and opportunities in solar PV waste management in India: A techno-economic and social perspective', in *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering*. Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore, pp. 195–204.
67. Santos, J.D. and Alonso-García, M.C. (2018) 'Projection of the photovoltaic waste in Spain until 2050', *Journal of cleaner production*, 196, pp. 1613–1628. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.05.252>.
68. Serpe, A. et al. (2024) '2002–2022: 20 years of e-waste regulation in the European Union and the worldwide trends in legislation and innovation technologies for a circular economy', *RSC Sustainability* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1039/d4su00548a>.
69. Sethuraman, N.R. (2024) *India mandates use of locally made solar cells in government projects from June 2026*, Reuters.com. Available at: <https://www.reuters.com/business/energy/india-mandates-use-locally-made-solar-cells-clean-energy-projects-june-2026-2024-12-10/> (Accessed: 6 January 2025).
70. Sharma, P., Verma, S. and Kumar, N. (2021) 'Recycling Challenges of Solar Photovoltaic Panels in India', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 278, pp. 124–136.
71. Sica, D. et al. (2018) 'Management of end-of-life photovoltaic panels as a step towards a circular economy', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 82, pp. 2934–2945. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.10.039>.

72. Singh, R. and Gupta, A. (2020) 'Solar Panel Waste Management in India: Challenges and Opportunities', *Renewable Energy Journal*, 45(3), pp. 123–135.
73. Spaes, J. (2021) *New delamination technique for PV module recycling*, *PV magazine International*. Available at: <https://www.PV-magazine.com/2021/03/19/new-delamination-technique-for-PV-module-recycling/> (Accessed: 11 December 2024).
74. 'Status of PV Module Recycling in Selected IEA PVPS Task 12 Countries' (2022) *IEA-PVPS*, 24(2022).
75. stiftung ear (2022) *stiftung elektro-altgeräte register*, *Stiftung-ear.de*. Available at: <https://www.stiftung-ear.de/en/about-us/who-we-are> (Accessed: 15 December 2024).
76. Suresh, Singhvi and Rustagi (2019) *Managing India's PV module waste*, *BRIDGE TO INDIA*. Available at: <https://bridgetoindia.com/report/managing-indias-PV-module-waste/> (Accessed: 6 December 2024).
77. Tatapower (2024) *Business Responsibility and Sustainability Report*, *Tatapower.com*. Available at: https://www.tatapower.com/content/dam/tatapoweraemsitesprogram/tatapower/pdf-root/sustainability/business-responsibility-report/BRSR_FY24.pdf?utm_source=chatgpt.com (Accessed: 8 January 2025).
78. Tyagi & Kuldeep (2021) *How India can Manage Solar Photovoltaic Module Waste Better*, *Ceew.in*. Available at: <https://www.ceew.in/publications/how-can-india-manage-photovoltaic-solar-panel-waste-disposal> (Accessed: 6 December 2024).
79. Tyagi et al., (2024) *Enabling a Circular Economy in India's Solar Industr*, *Ceew.in*. Available at: <https://www.ceew.in/publications/how-can-india-enable-circular-economy-with-solar-energy-waste-management-disposal> (Accessed: 6 December 2024).
80. Tyagi (2020) *Managing India's clean energy waste: A roadmap for the solar and storage industry*, *Teriin.org*. Available at: <https://www.teriin.org/article/managing-indias-clean-energy-waste-roadmap-solar-and-storage-industry> (Accessed: 5 December 2024).
81. UK Government (2018) *Regulations: Waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE)*, *Gov.uk*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/regulations-waste-electrical-and-electronic-equipment> (Accessed: 15 December 2024).
82. UmweltBundesamt (2019) *45%-target collection rate for WEEE reached in 2017*, *Umweltbundesamt*. Available at: https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/en/press/pressinformation/45-target-collection-rate-for-weee-reached-in-2017?utm_source=chatgpt.com (Accessed: 4 January 2025).

83. Us Epa, O. (2021) 'End-of-life solar panels: Regulations and management'. Available at: <https://www.epa.gov/hw/end-life-solar-panels-regulations-and-management> (Accessed: 15 December 2024).
84. Weckend, S., Wade, A. and Heath, G. (2016) *End-of-life Management of Solar Photovoltaic Panels*. Edited by IRENA & IEA-PVPS.
85. WEEE Forum (2021) *Issues associated to photovoltaic panels and compliance with EPR legislation*, *Weee-forum.org*. Available at: <https://weee-forum.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/WEEE-Forum-PV-Panels-Issue-Paper-2021-Final.pdf> (Accessed: 5 January 2025).

Appendices

Appendix 1 Recycling expo ID card

Appendix 2 Participation information sheet

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Title of Study: Sustainable Solar Energy in India: A Circular Economy Approach with Extended producer responsibility

Invitation

We would like to invite you to participate in this research project. You should only join if you want to; choosing not to participate will not disadvantage you. Before you decide if you wish to take part, you need to understand why the research is being done and what your participation will involve. If you have any questions you can contact us using the contact details at the end of this information sheet.

What is the purpose of the study?

This study aims to: Identify the key technological, economic, and policy challenges hindering the development of solar panel waste management and circularity in India and how can EPR policies be adapted to address these challenges.

Who is responsible for this study?

This study is the responsibility of Jalaj Handa at the University of Surrey.

Why have I been invited to take part?

You are invited to participate in this study because you are over 18 years old and your experience, role or perspective aligns with the study objectives, and your input is considered valuable for the success of this project. You were identified either from a public website, social media channels, the researcher's contacts, or from recommendations of a research participant.

Do I have to take part?

Participation is voluntary, and you do not have to take part. We will describe the study in this information sheet and will give you at least two days to read this, so you can decide whether you wish to take part in this study. Please contact us if there is anything that is not clear, or if you have any questions, or if you would like more information.

What happens if I do not want to take part or if I change my mind?

You are free to withdraw any time prior to attending the interview or during the interview without giving a reason, and only up to one month after the interview has been completed. After this point, as the interview will be transcribed and fully anonymised, it will not be possible to remove the information you have provided. We will delete all personal

information provided by you. You can simply email the research team using the contact details provided at the end of this information sheet.

If you withdraw from attending or during the interview, we will unfortunately not be able to provide you with a gift voucher or a donation to a charity of your choice (see below).

How is the project being funded?

This research is a part of an academic programme.

Will my participation be kept confidential?

We are responsible for making sure your participation is kept confidential and any data is kept secure and used only in the way described in this information sheet. All the information that we collect about you during the course of the research will be kept strictly confidential and only accessed by either member of the research team or responsible members of the University for auditing and/or monitoring purposes. You will not be able to be identified in any ensuing reports or publications.

Will my data be shared or used in future research studies?

We would like your permission to use anonymised data in future research studies, and to share them with other researchers (e.g. in open access databases, UK Data repository). This will be restricted to de-identified (anonymised) transcripts, and non-commercial use only. All personal information that could identify you will be removed or changed before information is shared with other researchers or results are made public. Your information may be subject to review for monitoring and audit purposes, by individuals from the University of Surrey and/or regulators who will treat your data in confidence.

What will happen to the results of the study?

This research and its findings will be summarised and disseminated through publication (journals, newsletter, bulletins, websites, reports, theses), dissertation, presentation, conferences or depositing data in an archive. Any published findings or quotations will either use pseudonyms or unidentifiable code, and will maintain your confidentiality and anonymity. You will not be personally identified in any reports or publications.

You can contact the study team to find out the results of the research. Contact details are provided at the end of this information sheet.

What will happen to my personal data?

As a publicly-funded organisation, we have to ensure that when we use identifiable personal information from people who have agreed to take part in research, that this data is processed fairly and lawfully. The University of Surrey processes personal data for the purposes of carrying out research in the public interest and special category data is processed on an additional condition necessary for research purposes. This means that when you agree to take part in this research study, we will use and look after your data in the ways needed to achieve the outcomes of the study.

Your personal data will be held and processed in the strictest confidence, and in accordance with current data protection regulations. When acting as the data controller, the University will keep identifiable information about you, i.e. your email address plus the email correspondences about this study (upon your consent) and your consent form, on its secure server for 10 years after the study has finished. During this period, only the research team can request to access them. As mentioned above, the other format of your personal data, i.e. audio-recording of your interview, will be destroyed securely and permanently immediately after it has been transcribed. This should be within six months after the interview has completed. In the meantime, the recording will be stored securely on the University server with password protection and be accessed only by the research team.

Your rights to access, change or move your information are limited, as we need to manage your information in specific ways in order for the research to be reliable and accurate. If you decide to withdraw from the study, we may not be able to withdraw your data. However, we will not use personally-identifiable information about you that we have already obtained to complete the study.

If you wish to make a complaint about how we have handled your personal data, you can contact our Data Protection Officer who will investigate the matter (dataprotection@surrey.ac.uk). If you are not satisfied with our response or believe we are processing your personal data in a way that is not lawful, you can complain to the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) (<https://ico.org.uk/>).

You can find out more about how we use your information <https://www.surrey.ac.uk/information-management/data-protection> and/or by contacting dataprotection@surrey.ac.uk.

What if you have a query or something goes wrong?

The ethical and governance conduct of this individual research project is the responsibility of the research supervisor <name> who agrees to abide by the pre-approved standardised protocol. Should you have any concerns on this, please email the University's Research Integrity & Governance office at: RIGO@surrey.ac.uk

If you are unsure about something you can contact the research team for further advice using the contact details at the bottom of this information sheet.

However, if your query has not been handled to your satisfaction, or if you are unhappy and wish to make a formal complaint to someone independent of the research team, then please contact:

Research Integrity and Governance Office (RIGO)

Research and Innovation Services

University of Surrey

Senate House, Guildford, Surrey, GU2 7XH

Phone: +44 (0)1483 689110

Email: rigo@surrey.ac.uk

The University has in place the relevant insurance policies which apply to this study. If you wish to complain or have any concerns about any aspect of the way you have been treated during the course of this study, then you should follow the instructions given above.

Who should I contact for further information?

If you have any questions or require more information about this study, please contact the research team or their supervisor using the following contact details:

Research student's name: Jalaj Handa

Research student's University of Surrey contact details: jh02815@surrey.ac.uk

Research supervisor's name: Lirong Liu

Research supervisor's University of Surrey contact details: lirong.liu@surrey.ac.uk

Thank you for reading this information sheet and for considering taking part in this research.

Appendix 3 Informed consent form

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Thank you for considering taking part in this research.

Please complete this form after you have read the Information Sheet and/or listened to an explanation about the research.

Title of Study: Sustainable Solar Energy in India: A Circular Economy Approach with Extended producer responsibility

University of Surrey Participant Ref: 6858189

The person asking for your consent must explain the project to you before you agree to take part. If you have any questions about the Information Sheet or their explanation, please ask the researcher before you make your decision. You will be given a copy of this Consent Form and the Information Sheet to keep and refer to at any time.

By ***initialling*** each box, you are consenting to this part of the study. Any un-initialled boxes will mean that you DO NOT agree to that part of the study and this may mean you are ineligible for the study.

Taking part in the study		
	Statement	Please <i>initial</i> each box
1	I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet dated [xxxxxxxxxxxx] for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information and asked questions which have been answered satisfactorily.	
2	I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw any time prior to attending the interview or during the interview, without giving a reason, and only up to one month after the interview has been completed. I understand that data already collected can only be withdrawn up to one month after the interview.	
3	I understand that information I provide may be subject to review by responsible individuals from the University of Surrey and/or regulators for monitoring and audit purposes.	
4	I understand that information I provide will be used in various anonymised outputs, including journals, newsletter, bulletins, websites, reports, theses, dissertation, presentation, conferences or depositing data in an open access databases.	

5	I understand that my personal data, including this consent form, which link me to the research data, will be kept securely in accordance with data protection guidelines, and only be accessible to the immediate research team or responsible persons at the University.	
6	I understand any personal contact details collected about me, such as my phone number and address, will not be shared beyond the study team.	
7	I consent to the interview being audio-recorded.	
8	I consent to my audio recordings to be used for the purposes stated in the information sheet.	
9	I agree for my audio recordings to be transferred to professional transcription company external to the University of Surrey for the purposes described in the information sheet.	
10	I agree to take part in this study.	

Future use of the information in the study		
	Statement	Please <i>initial</i> each box
11	[Optional] I give permission for my de-identified data to be archived in an external data archive or open access databases (e.g. UK Data Archive) and shared anonymously with other researchers, in order to carry out future research (but not for commercial use).	
12	[Optional] I agree for my personal contact details to be stored for 10 years after the study has completed by the research team who may wish to invite me to participate in follow-up studies to this project, in	

	future research, or in other teaching & learning activities being conducted at the University of Surrey.	
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Signatures		
Name of Participant	Signature	Date
Name of Researcher Jalaj Handa	Signature	Date 05-09-24

Appendix 4 Interview questions

Interview Questionnaire for Stakeholder 3

1. Circular Economy and Design

- How do you see the role of product design in improving the recyclability of solar panels? Are there any specific design features that make recycling more efficient or difficult?
- In your opinion, how can solar panel manufacturers improve product design to reduce waste and enhance circularity throughout the product's lifecycle?

2. Challenges in Collection and Recovery

- What are the primary challenges you face in the collection and recovery of solar panels in India?
- How do you currently source end-of-life solar panels, and what improvements could be made to streamline this process? Collection centers?
- What role does the informal sector play in the collection of solar panels, and how do you collaborate with them (if at all)?

3. EPR Implementation and Stakeholder Collaboration

- How do you think the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) framework can be better implemented to support solar panel recycling in India?
- In your experience, what improvements can be made in terms of collaboration between manufacturers, installers, and recyclers for better collection and recovery?
- What additional support do you think the government can provide to formal recyclers to improve the efficiency of the recycling process?

4. Economic and Business Viability

- From a business perspective, what challenges do you face in making solar panel recycling economically viable?
- What incentives (financial, policy-based, etc.) would encourage formal recyclers to scale up operations and improve the economics of solar panel recycling in India?
- How do you perceive the future of solar panel recycling in India, and what key changes would help make it more profitable and sustainable?

5. Future Outlook and Recommendations

- How do you see the future of the solar panel recycling industry evolving in India, especially with the government's focus on EPR and circular economy principles?
- What recommendations would you make to improve the overall recycling ecosystem for solar panels in India?

Interview Questionnaire for Stakeholder 1

1. Circular Design and Usage

- What design features do you think are critical to extending the lifespan and durability of solar panels?
- How often do you engage with manufacturers regarding product design to ensure panels are easier to maintain, reuse, or recycle?
- Are there any specific challenges or opportunities in promoting circular usage within the solar panel lifecycle?

2. Installation Practices and Maintenance

- What role do installation practices play in improving the operational life of solar panels?
- How do you approach operations and maintenance (O&M) to maximize panel efficiency and longevity?
- Do you think the current market supports sufficient incentives for extending the lifespan of solar panels through better O&M practices?

3. Collection and End-of-Life (EOL) Management

- What happens to the solar panels you install once they reach the end of their lifespan?
- Have you faced any challenges in coordinating with collection or recycling entities for EOL panels?
- In your opinion, what systems could improve the collection and recovery process for solar panels in India?

4. EPR Implementation and Stakeholder Collaboration

- How familiar are you with the EPR rules for solar panels in India?
- What role do you think EPC companies should play in fulfilling EPR responsibilities?
- How can collaboration between EPC companies, manufacturers, and recyclers be improved to meet EPR targets?

5. Economic and Policy Considerations

- Do you think the current policies adequately address the financial challenges related to the recycling and recovery of solar panels?
- What economic or policy incentives would encourage EPC companies to take a more active role in circular economy practices?
- Are there opportunities to integrate "product-as-a-service" models into your business to support circularity and EPR goals?

6. Informal Sector and Future Outlook

- Have you ever worked with or considered partnering with informal sector entities for collection or recycling?
- How do you foresee the role of EPC companies evolving in a circular economy framework for solar panel management?
- What would be your recommendations to improve the sustainability and profitability of the solar panel lifecycle in India?

Interview Questionnaire for Stakeholder 3

1. General Background

- Can you share an overview of your journey in the solar energy sector and the challenges you've faced with large-scale solar project implementation?
- How do you see the current state of the solar energy market in India in terms of sustainability and stakeholder engagement?

2. Waste Management and End-of-Life Channels

- From your experience, what typically happens to damaged or broken solar panels during installation or transportation? Are there any informal channels, such as scrap dealers, handling this waste?
- What challenges do you see in creating a formal system for the collection and management of solar PV waste?
- Are there any models or practices from your projects that could inform a scalable waste management system for solar panels?

3. Circular Economy and Stakeholder Involvement

- Do you believe that stakeholder involvement, such as manufacturers, EPC companies, and recyclers, is currently adequate for addressing the end-of-life management of solar panels?
- In your opinion, should stakeholders like DISCOMs, SNAs, or project developers have mandated roles in EPR programs? What roles could they effectively play?

- How can the involvement of informal recyclers be integrated into formal waste management systems for better results?

4. Policy and Infrastructure

- How do existing policies, such as EPR or waste management regulations, support or hinder solar PV waste recycling in India?
- Do you believe that policy changes, such as subsidies or incentives for recyclers, could improve the waste management ecosystem for solar projects?
- How much impact does the lack of infrastructure, such as recycling plants or collection centers, have on the circularity of solar PV systems?

5. Future Outlook and Recommendations

- What do you think is needed to develop a reliable and efficient channel for handling solar PV waste across its lifecycle?
- How can B2B solar project developers like yourself contribute to fostering circularity in the industry, beyond project execution?
- Are there any innovative strategies or technologies that you think should be prioritized to improve waste management in the solar sector?

Interview Questionnaire for Stakeholder 5

1. General Background & Industry Insights:

- Can you share a brief overview of your career journey, particularly your transition into the solar energy sector and your experience with both B2B and B2C models?
- From your perspective, how have the solar energy market dynamics in India evolved over the last few years, especially in terms of technology adoption, consumer awareness, and policy support?
- What major challenges do you see in integrating sustainability into the growth of the solar industry, especially with respect to market penetration and scaling?

2. Sustainability & Circular Economy in Solar Energy:

- How would you define sustainability in the context of the solar energy sector, and what practices do you believe should be prioritized to ensure long-term viability and environmental responsibility?
- In your experience, how well are the concepts of circularity and life-cycle management being adopted within the solar industry? Are businesses actively planning for the recycling and reuse of solar panels?
- What role do you think solar energy companies, particularly those involved in installation and sales, play in promoting circular economy principles such as material recovery and waste management?

3. Customer Education & Market Awareness:

- How do you educate both your B2B and B2C customers about the importance of sustainability in solar energy systems, particularly regarding end-of-life management and recycling of solar panels?
- Do you think there is enough consumer awareness about the environmental impact of solar panel waste? If not, what strategies would be effective in improving this awareness?

4. Vendor & Stakeholder Collaboration:

- Could you share your thoughts on how different stakeholders—such as manufacturers, EPCs, installers, and recyclers—can collaborate more effectively to integrate sustainability into the supply chain and support the circularity of solar PV components?
- From a sales perspective, how do you manage vendor relationships to ensure not only profitability but also sustainability and long-term commitment to responsible practices (such as take-back schemes or EPR)?
- How can government bodies and regulatory authorities improve collaboration with private sector players to establish a more efficient and streamlined process for waste management and recycling in the solar energy sector?

5. Waste Management & Recycling Challenges:

- What are the primary challenges you've observed in managing solar PV waste in the Indian market, particularly regarding broken panels during transportation, installation, or operation? How can these challenges be addressed?
- How do you assess the role of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) in the management of solar panel waste? Do you believe that it needs more stringent enforcement to create a better recycling ecosystem?
- Have you encountered any practical or successful examples where a solar company has effectively integrated end-of-life management strategies into their operations? Could these strategies be scaled or adapted across the industry?

6. Technology and Innovation for Sustainability:

- In your view, how critical are technological innovations—such as smart monitoring, IoT, and RFID tracking—in improving the sustainability and lifecycle management of solar panels?
- What role do you think advances in design (e.g., modular systems, eco-friendly materials) and recycling technologies could play in making the entire solar PV industry more circular?
- Do you see any potential for emerging technologies (e.g., blockchain for tracking panels) to improve the transparency and efficiency of the recycling process for solar panels?

7. Policy, Regulation, and Business Strategy:

- How do current Indian policies—like net metering, open access, and EPR—impact the sustainability of solar energy systems? What policy gaps do you see, and how can they be addressed to encourage better lifecycle management of solar panels?
- How can businesses leverage these policies to promote sustainable practices and increase the adoption of circular economy models in solar energy projects?
- What changes or new policies would you like to see implemented by the government to support the growth of solar energy while also ensuring that end-of-life waste is managed responsibly?

8. Future Outlook & Strategic Growth:

- How do you foresee the role of solar energy companies evolving in the next 5 to 10 years, especially in relation to sustainability, waste management, and circular economy practices?
- What steps should businesses in the solar energy sector take to ensure that sustainability and profitability are balanced, and how can your company contribute to this?

- With the growing demand for solar energy in India, what new business opportunities or market segments do you foresee emerging in the near future, especially in the context of recycling and waste management?

9. Closing Thoughts:

- What advice would you give to companies or entrepreneurs looking to scale their operations in the solar industry while integrating sustainable and circular practices into their business models?
- How do you think India's solar energy sector can become a global leader in sustainability, especially with the rapid growth and increasing focus on recycling and responsible waste management?

Interview Questionnaire for Stakeholder 4

1. Career and Leadership Journey

- Can you share the key milestones in your career that shaped your leadership approach in the solar energy sector?
- What challenges and opportunities do you see for leaders in balancing operational goals with the long-term sustainability of the solar industry?
- How has your leadership style evolved in response to market changes and policy shifts in the renewable energy space?

2. Market Trends and Growth

- How have you seen the solar energy market evolve in terms of adoption, innovation, and customer awareness?
- What are the emerging trends in the rooftop and utility-scale solar segments, and how do you foresee their impact on the renewable energy ecosystem?
- What role does digitalization (e.g., IoT, AI tools) play in transforming operations and customer engagement in the solar industry?

3. Policy and Regulatory Framework

- In your opinion, how effective are India's current renewable energy policies in promoting solar adoption and sustainability?
- What changes or additions would you recommend to improve the implementation of policies like net metering, open access, and rooftop solar incentives?
- How do you think global sustainability goals and frameworks, like those of Petronas Group, align with local solar energy regulations?

4. Circular Economy and End-of-Life Management

- With solar PV waste projected to rise in the coming years, how do you see the industry addressing end-of-life (EoL) challenges for solar panels?
- Are there any specific steps being taken—or that need to be taken—by manufacturers, installers, and recyclers to integrate circular economy principles into the solar value chain?
- What role do you envision for Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) in enabling efficient collection and recycling of end-of-life solar components?

5. Stakeholder Collaboration

- How important is collaboration between public and private stakeholders (e.g., policymakers, DISCOMs, recyclers) in driving a sustainable solar ecosystem?
- What are some ways to better involve stakeholders in programs like EPR or in building infrastructure for solar PV recycling?
- Can you share any examples of successful multi-stakeholder initiatives that have contributed to the growth or sustainability of the solar sector?

6. Strategic Vision and Future Prospects

- As a senior leader, how do you balance short-term business objectives with long-term sustainability goals?
- What are the key enablers for making solar PV recycling a viable and profitable industry in India?
- How do you see India's solar energy landscape evolving over the next decade, and what challenges must be addressed to sustain this growth?

7. Customer-Centric Approach

- How can the solar industry better address customer concerns about the environmental impact of solar PV systems, especially at their end of life?
- What strategies or innovations could enhance customer participation in sustainable practices, such as panel recycling or maintenance programs?

8. Policy Advocacy and Recommendations

- What role do you see for large corporations, like Petronas Group, in advocating for stronger renewable energy policies and sustainability practices?
- If you were to propose a new policy or framework for the solar sector, what would it prioritize (e.g., incentives for recycling, stricter quality standards, etc.)?

9. Closing Reflections

- What advice would you give to policymakers, entrepreneurs, or professionals aiming to make a lasting impact in the solar energy sector?
- How do you stay ahead of trends and challenges in such a dynamic and rapidly evolving industry?

Interview questionnaire for Stakeholder 2

Section 1: Career and Leadership Journey

- Key milestones in your career that shaped your leadership approach in the solar energy sector.
- Challenges and opportunities for leaders in balancing operational goals with the long-term sustainability of the solar industry.
- How your leadership style has evolved in response to market changes and policy shifts in the renewable energy space.

Section 2: Market Trends and Growth

- Evolution of the solar energy market in terms of adoption, innovation, and customer awareness.

- Emerging trends in the rooftop and utility-scale solar segments and their impact on the renewable energy ecosystem.
- The role of digitalization (e.g., IoT, AI tools) in transforming operations and customer engagement in the solar industry.

Section 3: Policy and Regulatory Framework

- Effectiveness of India's current renewable energy policies in promoting solar adoption and sustainability.
- Recommendations for improving the implementation of policies like net metering, open access, and rooftop solar incentives.
- Alignment of global sustainability goals and frameworks, like those of Petronas Group, with local solar energy regulations.

Section 4: Circular Economy and End-of-Life Management

- Addressing end-of-life (EoL) challenges for solar panels as solar PV waste increases.
- Steps manufacturers, installers, and recyclers can take to integrate circular economy principles into the solar value chain.
- Role of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) in enabling efficient collection and recycling of end-of-life solar components.

Section 5: Stakeholder Collaboration

- Importance of collaboration between public and private stakeholders (e.g., policymakers, DISCOMs, recyclers) in driving a sustainable solar ecosystem.
- Ways to better involve stakeholders in programs like EPR or in building infrastructure for solar PV recycling.
- Examples of successful multi-stakeholder initiatives that have contributed to the growth or sustainability of the solar sector.

Section 6: Strategic Vision and Future Prospects

- Balancing short-term business objectives with long-term sustainability goals as a senior leader.
- Key enablers for making solar PV recycling a viable and profitable industry in India.
- How India's solar energy landscape may evolve over the next decade and challenges that must be addressed to sustain this growth.

Section 7: Customer-Centric Approach

- Addressing customer concerns about the environmental impact of solar PV systems, especially at their end of life.
- Strategies or innovations to enhance customer participation in sustainable practices, such as panel recycling or maintenance programs.

Section 8: Policy Advocacy and Recommendations

- Role of large corporations, like Petronas Group, in advocating for stronger renewable energy policies and sustainability practices.
- New policy or framework proposals for the solar sector, prioritizing incentives for recycling, stricter quality standards, etc.

Section 9: Closing Reflections

- Advice for policymakers, entrepreneurs, or professionals aiming to make a lasting impact in the solar energy sector.
- How to stay ahead of trends and challenges in such a dynamic and rapidly evolving industry.

Appendix 5 Thematic analysis

Key themes	Stakeholder insights	Supporting Observations/References
Challenges in Collection and Disposal of Solar Panels		
Non-segregation and lack of collection provision	S2: "Non-segregation at source; No separate disposal option; Awareness amongst municipal workers and ragpickers."	CSTEP (2023): Highlights absence of remote collection sites and inefficiencies in waste handling logistics.
Informal sector dominance	S3: "The informal collection network is intricate and highly optimized for cost."	Observations: Informal recyclers (kabadiwalas) operate efficient networks but lack safety measures, exposing workers.
High transportation costs	S1: "The transport cost and risks associated with broken panels make proper disposal commercially draining."	EU TCP (2021): Transport costs are a significant barrier in solar waste management globally.
Safety concerns	S6: "Handling sharp-edged panels without proper training poses safety hazards."	Observations: Workers exposed to hazardous materials, including lead and cadmium, without safety gear.

Stakeholder Collaborations for Solar PV Waste Management		
Need for policy enforcement and monitoring	S2: "Better enforcement of policies, better monitoring, subsidy, and recycling infrastructure."	EU TCP (2021): Emphasizes centralized monitoring and enforcement mechanisms under EPR.
Importance of stakeholder	S3: "When the policies are made,	Michael and Iyer (2022):

involvement	you take stakeholders. You involve stakeholders when you are forming a policy."	Collaboration between state and private sectors is critical for waste management efficacy.
Integration of informal collectors	S3: "Collection centers could help integrate formal and informal recycling sectors."	CSTEP (2023): Recommends formalizing informal collectors through monetary incentives and structured training programs.
Role of local communities and awareness	S2: "Community radio, posters, television, and schools can spread awareness."	Observations: Hyper-local awareness campaigns in local languages could boost engagement and participation.
Public-private partnerships (PPPs)	S4: "Private and public sector cooperation, like in Jamshedpur's e-waste management, can be replicated for solar waste."	London Recycling Expo: Highlights PPPs as essential for bridging infrastructure and funding gaps.

Policy Implementation Challenges in Solar PV Waste Management		
EPR implementation gaps	S1: "There's a lack of clarity, lack of knowledge, and lack of resources in the implementation of EPR policies."	MoEFC (2022): Existing E-Waste Rules lack practical implementation advice for solar-specific components.
Compliance incentives	S2: "Making EPR compliance mandatory for receiving licenses or certifications."	EU WEEE Directive: Mandates compliance through financial penalties and recycling targets.
Lack of decommissioning frameworks	S4: "There's no particular policy or framework which sees in a particular manner how developers should decommission projects."	CSTEP (2023): Highlights the need for detailed guidelines for decommissioning solar panels.
Centralized regulatory framework	S5: "A centralized regulatory framework is needed to streamline solar waste management across states."	EU TCP (2021): Centralized systems under EPR frameworks have demonstrated success in ensuring compliance and efficiency.
Financial incentives for compliance	S6: "Comprehensive policies and financial incentives like tax benefits can ensure proper waste management."	Jain, Sharma, and Gupta (2022): Recommends subsidies and tax rebates to offset compliance cost

Economic and Technological Considerations for Solar PV Waste Management		
Recycling costs	S5: "The recycling process can sometimes cost more than the module's current market value."	Observations: High recycling costs are a significant barrier, particularly in remote areas.

Localized recycling infrastructure	S4: "Localized recycling units reduce logistical costs and enhance efficiency."	CSTEP (2023): Suggests cluster-based recycling hubs near areas with high solar energy potential to reduce costs.
AI and IoT technologies	S4: "AI and robotics can segregate waste directly at sites, saving transportation and labor expenses."	Kayalvizhi et al. (2024): IoT-enabled lifecycle monitoring systems enhance compliance and recovery efficiency.
Secondary markets for recovered materials	S2: "Using metals in the body that have a higher market value could make recycling processes more practical and profitable."	EU TCP (2021): Stresses the importance of developing markets for materials like silicon and glass to stabilize demand.
Public-private partnerships (PPPs)	S2: "CSRs can work on it and fund projects related to solar panel recycling."	London Recycling Expo: PPPs essential for funding innovative recycling infrastructure and initiatives.

Future Outlook on Solar PV Waste Management		
Growth of the solar energy market	S4: "The solar energy market, particularly in India, has unfolded very well, and you can say a lot of capacity addition happening every year."	Observations: Exponential growth rate post-introduction of net metering policies and subsidies.
Circular economy alignment	S3: "Circularity of materials will improve as recycling infrastructure and regulations stabilize."	Radavičius et al. (2021): European models highlight financial sustainability of circular approaches.
Role of local manufacturing	S4: "India needs to develop its own infrastructure and quality standards to reduce dependency on imports."	Observations: Promoting local manufacturing reduces costs and dependency on imports.
Technology-driven solutions	S5: "IoT and remote monitoring could track performance and life cycle of solar panels."	Observations: IoT and AI technologies improve recycling efficiency and lifecycle tracking.
Education and awareness	S5: "Educating B2B and B2C customers on end-of-life management is key to promoting sustainability."	Observations: Awareness programs targeting consumers and businesses can enhance engagement in waste management systems.